

1 **An inhibitory gate for state transition in cortex**

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20 down states.

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22

23 **Abstract**

24 Large scale transitions between active (up) and silent (down) states during quiet wakefulness or
25 NREM sleep regulate fundamental cortical functions and are known to involve both excitatory and
26 inhibitory cells. However, if and how inhibition regulates these activity transitions is unclear. Using
27 fluorescence-targeted electrophysiological recording and cell-specific optogenetic manipulation in
28 both anesthetized and non-anesthetized mice, we found that two major classes of interneurons, the
29 parvalbumin and the somatostatin positive cells, tightly control both up-to-down and down-to-up
30 state transitions. Inhibitory regulation of state transition was observed under both natural and
31 optogenetically-evoked conditions. Moreover, perturbative optogenetic experiments revealed that
32 the inhibitory control of state transition was interneuron-type specific. Finally, local manipulation of
33 small ensembles of interneurons affected cortical populations millimetres away from the modulated
34 region. Together, these results demonstrate that inhibition potently gates transitions between
35 cortical activity states, and reveal the cellular mechanisms by which local inhibitory microcircuits
36 regulate state transitions at the mesoscale.

37

38 **Introduction**

39 The mammalian brain generates internal activities independent of environmental stimuli (Destexhe,
40 2011). For example, during quiet wakefulness or NREM sleep the cortex and other brain regions
41 (e.g., the thalamus) display rhythmic electrical signals characterized by large-amplitude and low
42 frequency (< 1 Hz) oscillations (Metherate et al., 1992; Steriade et al., 1993a; Crunelli and Hughes,
43 2010; Halassa et al., 2014; Slezia et al., 2011; Fogerson and Huguenard, 2016; Herrera et al.,
44 2016; Sellers et al., 2015). These peculiar activities, named slow oscillations, are dominated by
45 recurring transitions between active (up) and silent (down) periods. In the cortex, up states are
46 associated with sustained membrane potential depolarization in single pyramidal neurons and
47 enhanced firing at the network level, while down states are characterized by membrane
48 hyperpolarization and reduced circuit firing (Steriade et al., 1993b; Contreras and Steriade,

49 1995;Vyazovskiy et al., 2009). The alternation between these two activity states plays fundamental
50 roles in regulating crucial cortical processes, such as the modulation of sensory inputs (Petersen et
51 al., 2003a;Crochet et al., 2005;Haider et al., 2007;Reig and Sanchez-Vives, 2007;Reig et al., 2015),
52 the consolidation and potentiation of memory (Marshall et al., 2006;Rasch et al., 2007), the
53 improvement of task performance (Huber et al., 2004) and the control of synaptic plasticity
54 (Vyazovskiy et al., 2009;Vyazovskiy et al., 2008). Although the cellular mechanisms regulating up
55 and down state transitions have been the focus of intense research, the role of many prominent
56 cortical circuits in these phenomena still remains elusive. One such example is cortical inhibition
57 (Crunelli et al., 2015). Previous studies found that inhibitory cells are active (Steriade et al.,
58 2001;Gentet et al., 2010;Tahvildari et al., 2012;Neske et al., 2015) and that there is a tight interplay
59 of excitatory and inhibitory conductances during the up state (Shu et al., 2003;Haider et al., 2006).
60 Since neither a gradual buildup nor a sudden increase in inhibition near the termination of the up
61 state was observed, these seminal data were interpreted against an active role of inhibition in the
62 transition from an up to a down state (Shu et al., 2003;Haider et al., 2006;Neske, 2015;Sanchez-
63 Vives et al., 2010). Moreover, in silico model of cortical dynamics showed that up-to-down
64 transitions can occur in the presence of an activity-dependent K^+ conductance with minor
65 contribution of synaptic inhibition (Compte et al., 2003), further arguing against a major role of
66 inhibition in shaping network shifts from the up to the down state. However, pharmacological
67 blockade of $GABA_A$ (Sanchez-Vives et al., 2010) and $GABA_B$ (Mann et al., 2009) receptors
68 significantly modifies the duration and the frequency of up and down states and other modelling
69 work showed that inhibition may actually contribute to facilitate the up-to-down transition
70 (Bazhenov et al., 2002;Chen et al., 2012). Furthermore, paired recordings in anesthetized and
71 naturally sleeping cats demonstrated that bursts of inhibitory activity do precede the onset of the
72 down state, suggesting a potential role of inhibition in the control of up-to-down transitions
73 (Lemieux et al., 2015).

74

75 In this study, we combined two-photon targeted single neuron electrophysiological recordings,
76 phase-locking analysis, and cell-specific optogenetic perturbations in anesthetized and non-
77 anesthetized awake mice to investigate the *causal* contribution of specific inhibitory circuits,
78 including parvalbumin (PV) and somatostatin (SST) interneurons, in the regulation of cortical state
79 transitions. Our data demonstrate that optogenetic modulation of interneurons precisely regulates
80 network up-to-down state shifts and reveals a previously unacknowledged role of the inhibitory
81 network in the control of down-to-up state transitions. This bidirectional (*up-to-down* and *down-to-*
82 *up*) inhibitory control of state transition is interneuron-type specific and finely controlled at the
83 microcircuit level, with local ensemble of active interneurons gating state transitions over
84 millimetres of cortical territories.

85

86 **Results**

87 To determine if and how PV and SST interneurons control state transitions, we first characterized
88 the spiking activities of these two cellular subpopulations during spontaneous up and down states in
89 anesthetized mice. To this aim, we performed two-photon-targeted juxtosomal electrophysiological
90 recordings in *Pvalb^{Cre}* (here called PV-Cre) \times TdTomato and *Sst^{Cre}* (here called SST-Cre) \times
91 TdTomato mice while simultaneously monitoring network activities with a LFP electrode (Fig. 1).

92

93 Up states (pink in Fig. 1b, g) and down states (purple) were identified from the LFP using an
94 established method (Saleem et al., 2010; Mukovski et al., 2007) which was fine-tuned to our
95 experiment by validating it against “ground truth” data made of simultaneous recordings of
96 membrane potentials of pyramidal neurons and the LFP (see Materials and Methods and Figure 1 -
97 Figure Supplement 1). Importantly, this method optimally combined several variables extracted
98 from the LFP to best estimate the network state (up or down, Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1). A
99 crucial variable in this detection algorithm was the LFP phase in the low frequency band, which
100 could thus be considered a good indicator of network state (Saleem et al., 2010) (see also Materials

101 and Methods). Phases between 112 and 264 degrees (the “trough” regions of the LFP slow
102 oscillatory component) mainly corresponded to up states and phases between 322 and 45 degrees
103 (the “peak” LFP regions) mainly corresponded to down states (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1h, i).
104 The LFP-based identification of states performed well on ground truth data, minimizing the
105 percentage of misclassified periods (i.e., false positives) at $6.0 \pm 0.2\%$ and $4.0 \pm 0.1\%$ for up and
106 down states, respectively (see Materials and Methods and Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1j).

107
108 Both interneuron types preferentially discharged action potentials (APs) during up states (Fig. 1c, h)
109 in agreement with previous reports (Puig et al., 2008; Tahvildari et al., 2012; Neske et al., 2015).
110 However, we found that a small but significant fraction of spikes ($p < 1E-2$ in 16 out of 16 PV cells
111 from 5 animals and $p < 4E-2$ in 15 out of 19 SST neurons from 7 animals, see Materials and
112 Methods for details on the statistical test) occurred during down states both for PV and SST cells
113 (Fig. 1 c, h). The percentage of up states in which the recorded interneuron fired (named active up
114 states) was higher than the percentage of down states displaying cell firing (called active down
115 states) (Fig. 1d, i) and the number of spikes per active up state was higher than the number of spikes
116 per active down state for both PV cells and SST interneurons (Fig. 1 e, j). Moreover, the average
117 firing rate, the percentage of active up and active down states, and the average number of spikes
118 fired during active up or down states was significantly higher for PV cells compared to SST
119 interneurons (active up states, $p = 4E-8$, unpaired Student’s *t*-test; active down states, $p = 2E-4$,
120 Mann-Whitney test; # of spikes per active up state, $p = 3E-6$, Mann-Whitney test; # of spikes per
121 active down state: $p = 1E-3$, Mann-Whitney test; PV, $N = 16$ cells from 5 animals; SST, $N = 19$
122 cells from 7 animals).

123
124 *Interneuron firing correlates with changes in the low frequency LFP phase*

125 The results in Fig. 1 suggest that PV and SST interneurons do not fire uniformly during the LFP
126 slow oscillation cycle, for example with more elevated firing during the up state with respect to

127 down state. To quantitatively investigate this temporal relationship, we computed, for each recorded
128 neuron, the distribution of phase at the exact time at which spikes were fired (i.e. “phase of firing”
129 distribution, Fig. 2). This is shown in Fig 2b, h for one representative PV cell and one representative
130 SST neuron, respectively. Locking to the slow wave phase was significant for all 16/16 PV and
131 15/15 SST neurons (Rayleigh test, $p < 2E-30$ for PV interneurons and $p < 7E-7$ for SST
132 interneurons, see also Materials and methods). Across the population PV and SST neurons
133 preferentially fired during the first half of the up state and the average preferred phase of firing was
134 167 ± 5 degrees and 170 ± 5 degrees for PV and SST interneurons, respectively (Fig. 2c, i).
135 However, these neurons fired also during phases associated to the second half of the up state, as
136 exemplified by the spread of the phase of firing distribution over phase angles in Figs. 2c, i. The
137 phase bins characterized by strong firing were also those where spikes were fired more reliably
138 across trials (Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 1 and 2, see also Materials and Methods).

139

140 The relationship between spike timing of PV/SST interneurons and the phase of slow LFP
141 oscillation can imply either that the firing of interneurons causally leads to changes in network
142 phase (and thus causes changes in network states) or that interneurons are entrained to the slow
143 oscillation of network activity and thus fire at specific phases. To disambiguate between these two
144 scenarios, we followed (Siapas et al., 2005; Eschenko et al., 2012) to take advantage of the fact that
145 the slow oscillation is not constant in frequency but shows small frequency fluctuations over time.
146 We shifted the LFP backward or forward by an amount τ , and we computed the strength of phase
147 locking of spikes (quantified as one minus the circular variance of the phase of firing distribution)
148 as a function of the time shift τ for each recorded interneuron. We reasoned that if spike times have
149 a causal effect on slow wave dynamics, then the LFP phase dynamics will be better predicted by the
150 structure of past spike times, thereby leading to higher phase locking values for *negative* shifts of
151 the LFP with respect to the firing activity of interneurons. In the absence of such causal effect, i.e.
152 slow network oscillations determining when interneurons fire, we expect that LFP phase dynamics

153 better relate to the structure of spike times in the future, thereby leading to higher phase locking
154 values for *positive* shifts of the LFP.
155
156 The dependence of the locking strength on τ is shown in Fig. 2d, j for one representative PV cell
157 and one SST neuron, respectively. Typically, the locking strength was larger for negative time shifts
158 and it was maximal for negative time shifts τ in 15/16 PV and 13/15 SST neurons. This suggests
159 that the spike-phase relationships reflect that firing of interneurons causes changes in phase
160 dynamics more than they reflect interneuron's firing being enslaved by the slow oscillatory
161 component of the LFP. We estimated the temporal extent of the putative causation of interneurons
162 on the slow LFP oscillation as the range of negative time shifts for which the time-shifted phase
163 locking was significant ($p < 0.01$, Rayleigh test, Bonferroni corrected) and higher than the maximal
164 value of time shifted locking for $\tau \geq 0$ (i.e., higher than the maximal value that could be explained
165 by non-causal effects only). The average value of the maximal temporal extent of causation, τ_{end}
166 (red asterisk in Fig. 2d, j), was -221 ± 41 ms for PV interneurons and -189 ± 30 ms for SST
167 interneurons. The value of the maximal causation, τ_{max} (green asterisk in Fig. 2d, j), was -93 ± 19
168 ms, significantly lower than zero ($p = 1\text{E-}4$, one-tailed one-sample Student's t-test, $N = 16$ from 5
169 animals) for PV cells and -81 ± 13 ms ($p = 1\text{E-}5$, one-tailed one-sample Student's t-test, $N = 15$
170 cells from 7 animals) for SST neurons.

171

172 To better visualize what these causation time ranges may imply, we computed the preferred phase
173 of firing as the median of the corresponding phase of firing distribution in both PV and SST
174 interneurons for $\tau = 0$, $\tau = \tau_{\text{max}}$ and $\tau = \tau_{\text{end}}$. As displayed in Fig. 2c, i, when $\tau = 0$ both PV and SST
175 interneurons preferentially fire during the first part of the up state. For $\tau = \tau_{\text{max}}$ and $\tau = \tau_{\text{end}}$, the
176 preferred phase of firing was shifted for both classes of interneurons towards the second half and
177 the end of the up state (for $\tau = \tau_{\text{max}}$, 192 ± 6 degrees and 190 ± 4 degrees for PV and SST,
178 respectively, Fig. 2e, k, left panels; for $\tau = \tau_{\text{end}}$, 215 ± 7 degrees and 213 ± 9 degrees for PV and

179 SST respectively, Fig. 2e, k, right panels). This analysis suggests that the firing activity of
180 interneurons, which primarily occurred in the first part of the up state, exerts maximal causation in
181 the latter part of the up state, including its end.

182 To investigate the nature of such statistical influences of spikes on future changes in slow LFP
183 dynamics and state ends, we further analyzed the changes in LFP phase speed in proximity to the
184 state ends, over the putative causal time range determined above. Given that phase is a good proxy
185 of state dynamics, decreases and increases in phase speed following a spike near the end of a state
186 may be interpreted as the spike delaying or anticipating the state end, respectively. We quantified
187 the mean changes in phase speed triggered to a spike time prior to the end of an up and down state
188 (Fig. 2f, 1 and Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 3). We found that, on average, phase speed
189 significantly increased after a PV spike (Fig. 2f, top panel) and a SST spike (Fig. 2l, top panel) near
190 the end of an up state. In contrast, phase speed significantly decreased (Fig. 2f, bottom panel) after a
191 PV spike near the end of a down state, while no significant effect (Fig. 2l, bottom panel) was found
192 for SST neurons. This latter result is probably influenced by the paucity of recorded spikes in the
193 considered time range (see Fig. 2 legend). To rule out the possibility that these changes in phase
194 speed are related to stereotyped asymmetries in LFP shapes near the end of a state that have nothing
195 to do with the spiking activity of interneurons, we compared these spike-triggered phase speed
196 results with “control” samples of LFP phase speed near state ends observed in the absence of
197 interneuron spikes (see Materials and Methods for details). Importantly, we found that the decreases
198 in speed in down states for PV cells and the increases in speed in up states for PV and SST neurons
199 around the center of the control stretches, computed exactly as with the real data triggered to a spike
200 time, were not significant (for up state stretches, $p = 8E-1$, one-tailed paired Student’s t -test, $N =$
201 8911 stretches from 16 PV cells and $p = 9E-1$, $N = 1346$ stretches from 15 SST cells; for down state
202 stretches, $p = 1E-1$, one-tailed paired Student’s t -test, $N = 199$ stretches from 11 PV cells and $p =$
203 $2E-1$, $N = 12$ stretches from 7 SST cells). Thus, we conclude that our results could not be explained

204 purely by stereotyped asymmetries in the LFP wave near state ends that are observed also in the
205 absence of interneuron spikes.

206

207 To investigate whether any of the phase of firing distribution features displayed in Figure 2b, h
208 correlated at the single cell level with the phase speed changes observed around interneuronal firing
209 (Figure 2f, l), we first computed the spike-triggered phase speed change for each individual neuron.
210 In doing so, we focused only on phase speed changes triggered by spikes in the up state, because
211 only in this case enough spikes per neuron for a robust single-cell phase-speed-change analysis
212 were observed. We then analyzed the correlation of the phase speed change of each cell with
213 various different features of the phase of firing distribution in the up state. We found correlation
214 between the single-cell phase speed change and the circular variance of the phase of firing
215 distribution, which quantifies the width of the distribution, for both PV (correlation 0.67, $p = 5E-3$,
216 $N = 16$) and SST interneurons (correlation 0.59, $p = 3E-2$, $N = 14$). Cells with particularly large
217 distributions (circular variance ≥ 0.35) tended to show large speed change (Figure 2 - Figure
218 Supplement 4a). We also found correlation between single-cell phase speed changes and the
219 preferred phase of firing for both PV (circular-linear correlation 0.62, $p = 5E-2$, $N = 16$) and SST
220 cells (circular-linear correlation 0.74, $p = 2E-2$, $N = 14$). Cells with earlier preferred phase of firing
221 tended to show larger speed change (Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 4b). Preferred phase of firing
222 and circular variance, however, tended to be correlated across cells (Figure 2 - Figure Supplement
223 4c), making it difficult to dissociate the independent effect of each of these two variables on phase
224 speed changes.

225

226 Altogether, these findings led us to hypothesize that the firing of both SST and PV interneurons
227 during up states may causally contribute to their ending, whereas the firing of interneurons during
228 down state, at least for PV cells, may delay the transition from the down state to the up state.

229

230 *Optogenetic activation of interneurons triggers up-to-down transitions*

231 To directly test whether interneurons causally contribute to up-to-down state transitions, we
232 optogenetically activated PV and SST interneurons during spontaneous slow oscillations. Selective
233 expression of ChR2 in PV and SST interneurons was achieved using AAV injections in PV-Cre and
234 SST-Cre mice, respectively. Immunohistochemical (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 1) and
235 electrophysiological (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 2) characterization confirmed the specificity of
236 expression and functionality of the opsin. Using patch-clamp recording from layer II/III principal
237 neurons in injected PV-Cre and SST-Cre mice under anaesthesia (Fig. 3), we found that a brief
238 (duration: 10 ms) light stimulus applied during an ongoing up state generated a pronounced and
239 long-lasting hyperpolarization which outlasted the light stimulus and resembled a transition to a
240 down state (Fig. 3a-c, left panel, Fig. 3f-h, left panel) but with larger slope compared to
241 spontaneous events (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 3). All recordings were performed in the
242 proximity of the illuminated area (see Materials and Methods). When we observed the effect of the
243 optogenetic manipulation at the network level using extracellular LFP and MUA recordings, we
244 found similar results. Photoactivation of PV and SST cells during an ongoing up state resulted in a
245 sudden decrease in the power of high-frequency oscillations in the LFP and in the reduction of the
246 spike frequency in the MUA signal. Both effects outlasted the light stimulus and were compatible
247 with a full transition to a down state (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4a-e, Figure 3 - Figure
248 Supplement 5a-e). We then performed patch-clamp recordings in awake, head-restrained mice
249 during quiet wakefulness. Under these experimental conditions cortical activities were characterized
250 by frequent transitions between the up and the down states in accordance with previous reports
251 (Petersen et al., 2003b). Importantly, we found (Fig. 3c, h right panels and Figure 3 - Figure
252 Supplement 6) that the effect of optogenetic activation of PV and SST interneurons during an
253 ongoing up state was similar to that observed in anesthetized mice, ruling out any possible side
254 effect of anaesthesia.

255 Stimulation of PV and SST interneurons during a down state did not cause a significant change in
256 the membrane potential of the recorded neuron in both anesthetized (Fig. 3d, e left panel, Fig. 3i, j
257 left panel) and non-anesthetized mice (Fig 3e, j right panels and Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 6).
258 LFP and MUA experiments also confirmed no major effect of optogenetic activation of PV and
259 SST interneuron during cortical downstate (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4f - j; Figure 3 - Figure
260 Supplement 5f - j).

261

262 *Endogenous firing of interneurons controls up-to-down and down-to-up transitions*

263 Optogenetic stimulation elicits APs in ChR2-positive cells in a way that may not fully recapitulate
264 physiological firing patterns of cortical interneurons. To demonstrate that *endogenous* spiking
265 activity of interneurons controls up-to-down transitions, we expressed the inhibitory opsin
266 Archaeorhodopsin (Chow et al., 2010) (Arch) in either PV or SST cells. We first controlled that Arch
267 efficiently suppressed APs in PV (Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 1a-e) and SST (Figure 4 - Figure
268 Supplement 1f-j) interneurons. We then delivered yellow light stimuli ($\lambda = 594$ nm; duration, 500
269 ms) during up states in anesthetized and non-anesthetized (Fig. 4 and Figure 4 - Figure Supplement
270 2) mice. Optogenetic inhibition of PV and SST interneurons prolonged the up state for the whole
271 duration of the light stimulation, resulting in membrane potential depolarization in single pyramidal
272 neurons (Fig. 4a-c, and Fig. 4f-h and Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 2b, e). Moreover, optogenetic
273 inhibition of PV and SST cells caused a significant increase in the gamma frequency power and
274 spike frequency in the LFP and MUA signal, respectively (for PV cells Figure 4 - Figure
275 Supplement 3a-e; for SST interneurons, Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4a-e), events that were
276 compatible with a prolongation of the up state by the optical manipulation. After stimulus offset, we
277 observed a significant hyperpolarization of the membrane potential (Fig. 4c, h) that resembled a
278 transition to the down state in patch-clamp recordings in both PV and SST mice. In extracellular
279 recordings, the stimulus end was associated with a decrease in the power of high-frequency
280 oscillations in the LFP (Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3b, c, Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4b, c)

281 and of the MUA signal (Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3e; Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4e), results
282 which were again compatible with an up-to-down state transition at the end of the light stimulus.
283 PV and SST interneurons fire preferentially during cortical up states (Puig et al., 2008; Tahvildari et
284 al., 2012; Neske et al., 2015). However, our data (Fig. 1c, h) showed that PV and SST interneurons
285 fire also during down states and the bottom panel of Fig. 2f suggests that the low firing activity of
286 PV cells during the down state may influence down-to-up transition probability. To test this
287 hypothesis we inhibited PV and SST cells during ongoing down states. We found that individual
288 principal cells and the cortical network reliably transitioned to an active state, which resembled an
289 up state, upon photoinhibition of interneurons. Optogenetic inhibition of PV and SST cells during
290 an ongoing down state triggered a membrane depolarization in pyramidal cells in anesthetized and
291 non-anesthetized mice (Fig. 4d, e, i, j and Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 2c, f) which could over last
292 the light stimulus. When looking at the cortical network activity with extracellular recordings,
293 optogenetic inhibition of interneurons during an ongoing down state increased the power of high
294 frequency oscillations in the LFP (PV inhibition, Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3f-h; SST
295 inhibition, Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4f-h) and the MUA signal (PV inhibition, Figure 4 -
296 Figure Supplement 3i, j; SST inhibition, Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4i, j), effects which were
297 compatible with a full network transition to an up state.

298

299 *Inhibitory control of state transition is interneuron subtype-specific*

300 The previous experiments show that optogenetic inhibition of both PV and SST interneurons
301 prolonged the up state and favoured down-to-up transitions. However, important differences
302 between the effects of the manipulations of the two interneuron types were observed (Fig. 5). First,
303 suppression of PV, but not SST cells, during both up and down states significantly enhanced
304 spiking activity of principal cells (Fig. 5 a, b, d). In both anesthetized and non-anesthetized animals,
305 photoinhibition of SST interneurons during up states tended to increase the firing frequency of
306 principal neurons, but the effect did not reach statistical significance (Fig. 5f, g, i). Second,

307 photoinhibition of PV cells during spontaneous down states generated up state transitions with
308 shorter latency from the onset of the light stimulus compared to the photoinhibition of SST cells in
309 both anesthetized (Fig. 5c, h: average latency values: 69 ± 4 ms vs 181 ± 15 ms for PV and SST,
310 respectively; $p = 6E-5$, unpaired Student's t -test, PV $N = 11$ cells from 4 animals and SST $N = 9$
311 cells from 5 animals) and non-anesthetized mice (Fig. 5e, j: average latency values: 30 ± 5 ms vs 67
312 ± 11 ms for PV and SST, respectively $p = 9E-3$ unpaired Student's t -test, $N = 8$ cells from 5
313 animals for PV and 8 cells from 5 animals for SST). Third, inhibiting PV interneurons facilitated
314 down-to-up transitions with less jitter compared to the inhibition of SST cells (in anesthetized mice,
315 20 ± 3 ms for PV inhibition vs 109 ± 17 ms for SST inhibition, $p = 6E-4$, unpaired Student's t -test,
316 $N = 11$ PV cells from 4 animals and $N = 9$ SST cells from 5 animals; in non-anesthetized mice, 16.8
317 ± 2.9 ms for PV inhibition vs 32.7 ± 6.1 ms for SST inhibition, $p = 3E-2$, unpaired Student's t -test,
318 $N = 8$ cells from 5 animals for PV and SST interneurons). Fourth, photoinhibition of PV cells
319 triggered down-to-up transitions with larger slope compared to spontaneous transitions observed in
320 the same recorded cell. In contrast, photosuppression of SST cells triggered down-to-up transitions
321 with slopes that were indistinguishable from those of spontaneous down-to-up transitions (Figure 5
322 - Figure Supplement 1).

323

324 *Local optogenetic manipulation of interneurons induces mesoscale state transitions*

325 Our results showed that optogenetic perturbation of cortical interneurons control state transitions in
326 cortical cells and networks located in proximity to the illuminated area. Given that up and down
327 state transitions are known to occur over large cortical areas, we asked whether local optogenetic
328 perturbation of interneurons could also affect cortical regions far from the illuminated site. To
329 address this question, we first simultaneously recorded the MUA in two cortical regions that were
330 approximately 2 mm apart in anesthetized mice. The two electrodes (Ch1 and Ch2, Figure 6 -
331 Figure Supplement 1) were lowered to the same cortical depth (~ 350 μ m from the pial surface),
332 and light was delivered to the more rostral recording site (Ch1) using a fiber optic positioned

333 normal to the brain surface. In mice expressing ChR2 in PV cells, a short (duration: 10 ms) light
334 stimulus significantly reduced the MUA signal at both channels (Ch1 and Ch2, Figure 6 - Figure
335 Supplement 1a-e). Similar results were observed in mice expressing ChR2 in SST interneurons
336 (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 1f-j). To exclude the possibility that the effect on the MUA signal
337 recorded in Ch2 (i.e., the electrode placed in the most caudal area) was due to direct illumination
338 from the optical fiber placed near the rostral electrode (Ch1), we repeated these experiments using a
339 patterned illumination system using a digital micromirror device (DMD) to precisely control the
340 size of the illumination area. Consistent to what was previously observed, we found that the
341 activation of PV or SST in a confined area (area diameter, 200 μm) projected close to Ch1 similarly
342 affected network activities in both recording sites, resulting in a significant reduction of spike
343 frequency in the MUA signal recorded at Ch1 and Ch2 (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2).

344

345 We then tested the effect of local interneurons modulation on the membrane potential of cortical
346 neurons located far from the modulated region. To this aim, we performed dual patch-clamp
347 recordings from superficial pyramidal neurons in anesthetized (Fig. 6) mice. We found that light
348 stimulation induced significant membrane potential hyperpolarization in both recorded neurons
349 (Fig. 6a-c, g-i), efficiently driving cells from the up to the down state in both PV and SST mice
350 expressing ChR2 (PV: response delay between Ch2 and Ch1, 3.2 ± 0.6 ms; SST: response delay
351 between Ch2 and Ch1, 3.5 ± 1.1 ms, Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 3a-b). Similar results were
352 obtained in awake animals when recording from single pyramidal neurons located ~ 2 mm apart
353 from the stimulated area (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 4a-c, g-i). Finally, we extended this
354 experimental design to mice expressing Arch in PV or SST interneurons. Photoinhibition of PV or
355 SST interneurons in anesthetized animals enhanced network activity and significantly increased the
356 MUA signal during light stimulation at both recording sites (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 5).
357 Moreover, in paired recording experiments in anesthetized mice we found that photoinhibition of
358 PV or SST significantly facilitated down-to-up transitions in both recorded neurons (Fig. 6, d-f, j-l)

359 with variable response delays (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 3c-d). This was confirmed in awake
360 non-anesthetized animals, where we observed a significant membrane potential depolarization
361 during light stimulation in single recorded neurons located far (~ 2 mm) from the illuminated area
362 (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 4d-f,j-l).

363

364 **Discussion**

365 During low-arousal states such as quiet wakefulness, NREM sleep, and some forms of anesthesia,
366 cortical circuits display slow alternation of active (up) and silent (down) states (Steriade et al.,
367 1993b;Steriade et al., 1993a;Petersen et al., 2003a;Crochet and Petersen, 2006;Massimini et al.,
368 2004). These activities play a fundamental role in shaping network function and in regulating
369 fundamental cortical processes, including the modulation of sensory inputs (Petersen et al.,
370 2003a;Haider et al., 2007;Reig et al., 2015), the regulation of synaptic plasticity (Rosanova and
371 Ulrich, 2005;Vyazovskiy et al., 2008), and the control of memory consolidation (Diekelmann and
372 Born, 2010;Miyamoto et al., 2016;Rasch et al., 2007). Given the relevance of up and down states in
373 the control of cortical function, understanding the cellular mechanisms underlying the generation
374 and modulation of these fundamental network dynamics is of crucial importance. Since the initial
375 characterization of the up and down states of the slow oscillation using intracellular recordings
376 (Steriade et al., 1993b), a role of interneurons in mediating the hyperpolarizing component of the
377 up-to-down transitions was proposed. However, subsequent work has provided contradictory
378 evidence. Electrophysiological recordings from individual interneurons showed that these cells fire
379 during cortical up states (Steriade et al., 2001;Puig et al., 2008;Fanselow and Connors,
380 2010;Tahvildari et al., 2012;Neske et al., 2015) and perturbation of their activity during the up state
381 modifies cellular dynamics (Neske and Connors, 2016), showing that interneurons are actively
382 engaged during the up state. The timing of interneuronal spikes during the up state was shown to be
383 variable (Puig et al., 2008) and dependent on the specific subtype of interneuron that was
384 considered (Neske et al., 2015). Moreover, intracellular recordings *in vitro* and *in vivo* from

385 principal cortical neurons showed paralleled changes in excitatory and inhibitory conductance
386 during up state progression. Since no net increase nor gradual build-up of inhibitory conductance
387 with respect to excitatory ones at the end of the up state was observed (Shu et al., 2003; Tahvildari et
388 al., 2012; Neske et al., 2015), these data were taken against a role of interneurons in up state
389 termination. Computational work also suggested that slow oscillatory activity and up state
390 termination can occur in neural networks relying largely on adaptation currents in principal cells
391 with a minor role of inhibition (Compte et al., 2003). However, pharmacological blockade of
392 GABA_A receptors decreases the up state duration (Sanchez-Vives et al., 2010) and selectively
393 antagonism of GABA_B receptors increases up state duration (Mann et al., 2009). Moreover, recent
394 results pointed to a role of the GABA_A receptor in the synchronous termination of the up state
395 across different cortical areas (Lemieux et al., 2015), suggesting that interneurons may contribute to
396 terminate up states as also supported by other *in silico* work (Bazhenov et al., 2002; Chen et al.,
397 2012).

398

399 *Interneurons control the up-to-down transition*

400 In the present study we demonstrate that activity of the two major subtypes of cortical interneurons,
401 the PV and the SST positive cells, causally contribute to terminate cortical up states. Their causal
402 involvement was supported by two independent experimental approaches: *i*) in non-perturbative
403 experiments in which we measured the spike activity of identified interneuronal subtypes using
404 two-photon guided juxtosomal electrophysiological recordings while measuring network dynamics
405 with the LFP; *ii*) using bidirectional optogenetic perturbations of GABAergic cells to modulate their
406 firing activity while recording network and single cell activity with electrophysiology. In the first
407 approach, we found that interneuronal spikes are more strongly locked to future than to past
408 variations in the LFP phase, and that interneuronal spiking during up states was associated with
409 subsequent acceleration of the LFP phase speed (Fig. 2). In the second approach, we found that
410 brief optogenetic activation of either PV or SST interneurons resulted in the reduction of network

411 activities in extracellular LFP and MUA recordings (Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4-5). Moreover,
412 in intracellular patch-clamp experiments from principal neurons we observed membrane
413 hyperpolarization resembling a full transition to the down state following PV or SST optogenetic
414 activation (Fig. 3). In contrast, optogenetic inhibition of PV and SST interneurons during an
415 ongoing up state prolonged the up state for the entire duration of the light stimulus (Fig. 4), further
416 supporting that interneuronal firing contributes to up state termination. Our conclusions were
417 strengthened by finding compatible results for the causal role of these interneurons in slow
418 oscillation dynamics both with statistical analysis of fully unperturbed endogenous neural activity
419 (Fig. 2) and with optogenetic manipulations (Figs. 3-4). These results demonstrate the value of
420 optimally combining optogenetics with statistical analysis of neural activity recorded under
421 unperturbed natural conditions to dissect the causal role of specific circuit elements in network
422 dynamics (Panzeri et al., 2017).

423

424 These results do not contrast with previous studies reporting similar dynamics of inhibitory
425 conductances with respect to excitatory ones at the end of the up state (Shu et al., 2003; Haider et al.,
426 2007; Neske et al., 2015). First, the lack of a net increase of inhibition with respect to excitation at
427 the end of the up state does not necessarily exclude a causal role of interneurons in promoting up-
428 to-down transition. Second, conductance measurements that are typically averaged across
429 oscillation cycles may have hindered variable features of inhibitory networks associated to the
430 stochastic nature of cortical dynamics, as for example transient changes in interneuronal synchrony.
431 It may end up that up-to-down state transitions are associated with lower but more synchronous
432 firing activity in subsets of interneurons innervating specific compartments of principal neurons. To
433 test this hypothesis further experiments encompassing simultaneous LFP recordings and two-
434 photon calcium imaging from different subtypes of interneurons or multiple juxtosomal recordings
435 from identified GABAergic cells will be needed.

436

437 *Interneurons control the down-to-up transition*

438 Remarkably, our data also demonstrate a previously unrecognized role of interneurons in the control
439 of down state duration. Photo-inhibition of PV or SST interneurons during ongoing down states
440 triggered reliable transitions to active cortical states. These transitions resembled spontaneous up
441 states as they were characterized by membrane depolarization in intracellular recordings (Fig. 4), an
442 increase in gamma frequencies in the LFP and an augmentation of MUA signals at the network
443 level (Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3-4). These results were surprising given that interneurons were
444 commonly believed to be largely inactive during cortical down states (Timofeev et al.,
445 2001;Tahvildari et al., 2012) (but see also (Fanselow and Connors, 2010;Neske et al.,
446 2015;Ushimaru and Kawaguchi, 2015)). However, our juxtosomal electrophysiological recordings
447 *in vivo* showed that a small but significant fraction of interneuronal spikes also occurs in down
448 states. Based on these results, we propose that the weak firing activity of interneurons during
449 cortical down state is fundamental to maintain the cortical circuitry in the silent state, preventing it
450 from escaping into the up state. Chloride imaging across different compartments of pyramidal
451 neurons during up and down state transitions might be used as an alternative experimental approach
452 to further investigate this issue.

453

454 In this context it is interesting to evaluate how many spikes interneurons need to discharge to
455 maintain a cortical down state and how many spikes the optogenetic manipulations used in this
456 study are interfering with. To address these questions, we first estimated the number of illuminated
457 cells that we efficiently silenced during optogenetic inhibitory experiments by calculating the
458 volume of the illuminated brain region in which interneurons were reliably modulated by light and
459 the density of opsin positive cells under our experimental conditions (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement
460 6d-m, see Materials and Methods for details). Based on our calculations, we estimated that ~ 100
461 PV cells and ~ 650 SST neurons were efficiently modulated during our optogenetic manipulations.
462 From the data about spike activity of interneurons during down states reported in Fig. 1, we then

463 calculated that the optogenetic inhibitory manipulations displayed in Fig. 4 interfered with ~ 40 APs
464 in PV cells and about ~ 20 APs in SST interneurons during down states. These results suggest that
465 the GABAergic control of cortical state transition is surprisingly sensitive, with only a few tens of
466 APs fired by interneurons efficiently controlling down-to-up state transition.

467

468 *Inhibitory modulation of cortical state transition is interneuron-subtype specific*

469 The network effects of optogenetic manipulation of PV and SST interneurons were interneuronal
470 type specific. PV cells exerted a stronger effect on state transitions compared with SST interneurons
471 (Fig. 5), but manipulation of SST cells triggered state transitions that more closely resembled
472 spontaneous transitions compared to manipulation of PV interneurons. During both up and down
473 states, photo-inhibition of PV, but not SST interneurons, significantly increased the spiking activity
474 of pyramidal neurons. Moreover, PV photo-inhibition during down states increased the probability
475 of generating down-to-up transitions with shorter latencies and smaller temporal variance compared
476 to photo-inhibition of SST cells. Finally, optogenetic inhibition of SST, but not PV interneurons,
477 triggered down-to-up state transitions with slope similar to spontaneous transitions. These
478 differences in modulating the activity of pyramidal neurons can be explained based on at least three
479 different properties of PV and SST cells: *i*) the average firing rate; *ii*) the location of synaptic
480 contacts onto principal cells; *iii*) the strength of the synaptic connections. For example, the stronger
481 effect of PV photo-inhibition on network activities might be related to the higher firing activity of
482 PV cells compared to SST interneurons (Gentet et al., 2010; Gentet, 2012; De Stasi et al., 2016). In
483 line with this interpretation, the higher firing rate of SST cells in awake compared to anesthetized
484 animals¹⁹ may also explain the stronger effect of SST inhibition observed in awake compared to the
485 anesthetized condition (Fig. 5).

486

487 Although the phase locking (Figure 2b, h) and phase speed analysis (Figure 2f, l) on simultaneous
488 LFP and juxtosomal recordings do not show major differences between PV and SST cells,

489 optogenetic inhibitory manipulation of SST interneurons triggered cortical state transitions that
490 better resembled spontaneous transition compared to the same manipulation performed on PV cells.
491 These latter results could point to a more prominent role of SST cells in regulating cortical state
492 dynamics under physiological conditions. This would be in line with recent findings demonstrating
493 that SST firing activity is extremely sensitive to cortical states and strongly affected by cholinergic
494 inputs from subcortical areas (Gentet et al., 2010;Chen et al., 2015;Munoz et al., 2017).

495

496 It is worth noting that the lack of significant difference between the effect on up-to-down state
497 transition of optogenetic activation of PV and SST interneurons (Fig. 3) might be due to the
498 oversynchronous activity induced in interneurons by the brief light pulse that we used in the current
499 study. A ramp-like light stimulus (Adesnik and Scanziani, 2010) or stabilized step function opsins
500 (Berndt et al., 2009) coupled with minimal light intensity stimulation could be used to elevate
501 interneuronal excitability without explicitly controlling spike timing across the population. With
502 this approach, it might be easier to unmask differences between the various interneuron subtypes
503 because any sort of synchronous spiking would emerge from the natural statistics of the spike trains
504 of the population under study rather than be imposed by the optogenetic manipulation.

505

506 *Potential mechanisms driving interneuronal firing during down states*

507 Local excitatory connectivity between principal cells and interneurons contribute to drive the
508 activity of cortical inhibitory cells during the ongoing network dynamics (Dantzker and Callaway,
509 2000;Staiger et al., 2009;Apicella et al., 2012). An unanswered question is then what drives
510 interneurons to fire during cortical down states, when excitatory cells have been reported to be
511 largely silent. One possibility is that GABAergic cells undergo intrinsic oscillatory activity as for
512 example reported in (Le Bon-Jego and Yuste, 2007) or that neuromodulators may regulate the
513 excitability of interneurons (Chen et al., 2015). Alternatively, small subpopulations of excitatory
514 neurons were reported to fire during cortical down states (Neske et al., 2015;Ushimaru and

515 Kawaguchi, 2015) and this mechanism may drive certain interneurons to fire. A third possibility is
516 that long-range excitatory fibers from other brain regions may input onto local cortical interneurons.
517 In this regard, it is interesting to note that spiking activity of thalamic nuclei have been reported to
518 occur during cortical down states ahead of up state initiation and it has been proposed that the early
519 activation of thalamic nuclei contributes to the generation of up states by early activation of fast
520 spiking (FS) cells followed stimulation of pyramidal neurons (Ushimaru and Kawaguchi, 2015).
521 Our data are compatible with these experimental findings, but suggest that early activation of FS
522 interneurons may actually prevent, rather than favour, the up state initiation. While it is clear that
523 *strong* thalamic activation by means of electrical (MacLean et al., 2005;Reig and Sanchez-Vives,
524 2007;Reig et al., 2015;Watson et al., 2008) or sensory (Petersen et al., 2003a;Hasenstaub et al.,
525 2007;Civillico and Contreras, 2012) stimulation is a trigger for down-to-up state transitions in
526 cortex, our data are compatible with the scenario in which *weak* thalamic activation during cortical
527 down states preferentially induces suprathreshold activity in cortical FS interneurons (Hu and
528 Agmon, 2016) leading to a prolongation of the silent cortical state. In this framework, the
529 observation that SST interneurons are also active during cortical down states suggests that these
530 interneuronal cells may be similarly controlled by thalamic inputs (Tan et al., 2008).

531

532 *Local modulation of inhibition controls network states over large cortical territories*

533 Using simultaneous recordings of network and single cell activity in two brain regions located ~ 2
534 mm apart, we demonstrated that local activation of interneurons in one of the two regions during an
535 up state causes a transition to the down state that occurs near synchronously in both recorded areas
536 (Fig. 6 and Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 1). These results were not due to unwanted direct
537 illumination of both recorded cortical areas because we replicated these findings both with local
538 illumination through a fiber optic and with patterned illumination that precisely delivered light to
539 one restricted region of interest in the sample (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2). Previous reports
540 showed that up-to-down transitions occur with short (i.e. few milliseconds) delay among cortical

541 regions (Volgushev et al., 2006;Chen et al., 2012), but the mechanisms underlying this phenomenon
542 are not understood. Our data show that photoactivation of interneurons in one cortical region
543 promoted up-to-down transitions over large territories (up to 2 mm apart from the illuminated site)
544 with latencies as short (~ 3 ms) as the ones characterizing spontaneous up-to-down transitions
545 (Volgushev et al., 2006;Chen et al., 2012). This suggests that a sudden withdrawal of activity in a
546 confined cortical area can trigger synchronous mesoscale network transitions towards silent states.
547 Moreover, our data also show that photo-inhibition of interneurons during an ongoing up state
548 significantly affects network activity at distal cortical locations. When interneurons were locally
549 inhibited in one region during a down state a transition to the up state was reliably observed in two
550 recorded areas located > 2 mm apart (Fig. 6e, f, k, l), directly demonstrating a role of local
551 inhibition in the control of down state synchrony across cortical areas. This observation is also of
552 crucial importance for the correct interpretation of past works, where local optogenetic perturbation
553 of interneurons was used to silence activity and this manipulation was assumed to have an effect
554 mostly in the proximity of the illuminated area (Adesnik et al., 2012;Lee et al., 2012;Genet,
555 2012;Sachidhanandam et al., 2013).

556

557 In conclusion, our data provide important, new and quantitative insights in the role of distinct
558 inhibitory sub-networks in the control of cortical spontaneous dynamics. We show that the
559 discharge of a small number (few tens) of APs in specific classes of local interneurons controls
560 mesoscale state transitions in cortex. Because network state is known to powerfully and
561 dynamically modulate several cortical functions, including sensory processing (Petersen et al.,
562 2003a;Haider et al., 2007;Reig and Sanchez-Vives, 2007), our findings might have important
563 implications for the understanding of the cellular mechanisms underlying the dynamics of flexible
564 computational processes in the cortex.

565

566 **Materials and Methods**

567 *Animals*

568 Experimental procedures involving animals have been approved by the IIT Animal Welfare Body
569 and by the Italian Ministry of Health (authorization # 34/2015-PR and 125/2012-B), in accordance
570 with the National legislation (D.Lgs. 26/2014) and the European legislation (European Directive
571 2010/63/EU). The mouse lines B6;129S6-*Gt(ROSA)26Sor^{tm14(CAG-TdTomato)Hze}/J*, id #007908,
572 RRID:IMSR_JAX:007908 (otherwise called TdTomato line), *Pvalb^{Cre}*, B6.129P2-*Pvalb^{tm1(cre)Arbr}/J*,
573 id #017320, RRID:IMSR_JAX:017320 (called PV-cre line) and *Sst^{Cre}*, *Sst^{tm2.1(cre)Zjh}/J*, id #013044,
574 RRID:IMSR_JAX:013044 (called SST-cre line) were purchased from the Jackson Laboratory (Bar
575 Harbor, USA). The animals were housed in a 12:12h light-dark cycle in singularly ventilated cages,
576 with access to food and water *ad libitum*.

577

578 *Viral Injections*

579 The adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) AAV2.1.EF1a.DIO.hChR2(H134R)-EYFP.WPRE.hGH,
580 AAV2.1EF1.dflox.hChR2(H134R)-mcherry.WPRE.hGH, AAV2.1.flex.CBA.Arch-
581 GFP.WPRE.SV40, and AAV2.9.flex.CBA.Arch-GFP.WPRE.SV40 were purchased from the
582 University of Pennsylvania Viral Vector Core. PV-Cre, SST-Cre, PVxTdTomato, and
583 SSTxTdTomato transgenic mice (both males and females) were injected between postnatal day 0
584 (P0) and P2. Pups were anesthetized using hypothermia, placed on a custom-made stereotaxic
585 apparatus and kept at approximately 4°C for the entire duration of the surgery. The skull was
586 exposed through a small skin incision and ~ 250 nl of viral suspension were slowly injected using a
587 glass micropipette at stereotaxic coordinates of 0 mm from bregma, 1.5 mm lateral of the sagittal
588 sinus and 0.25-0.3 mm depth. Following injection the micropipette was held in place for 1-2
589 minutes before retraction. After pipette removal, the skin was sutured and the pup was revitalized
590 under an infrared heating lamp.

591

592 *Procedure for in vivo recordings*

593 Electrophysiological experiments were performed at postnatal day P24-P28 for PV-Cre mice and
594 P24-P30 for SST-Cre animals. For experiments performed in anesthetized animals, mice were
595 injected intraperitoneally with urethane (16.5%, 1.65g/kg). The body temperature was monitored
596 using a rectal probe and maintained at 37°C with a heating pad. Oxygen saturation was controlled
597 by a pulse oximeter (MouseOx, Starr Life Sciences Corp., Oakmont, PA). Respiration rate,
598 heartbeat, eyelid reflex, vibrissae movements, reactions to tail and toe pinching were monitored to
599 control the depth of anaesthesia throughout the surgery and the experiment. At the beginning of
600 surgical procedure, 2% of lidocaine solution was subcutaneously applied in the proximity of the site
601 of craniotomy. The position of the craniotomy was generally guided by the maximal intensity of the
602 fluorescence. In many experiments, this coincided with the somatosensory area of the neocortex.
603 Once the craniotomy was opened, the brain surface was kept moist with a HEPES-buffered artificial
604 cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF). The dura was removed with a metal needle only for extracellular
605 electrophysiological recordings. For simultaneous juxtosomal and Local Field Potential (LFP)
606 recordings (Fig. 1, 2, Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1 and Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 1-4) two
607 different craniotomies ($< 0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$) were performed at 0.5 mm distance one from the other,
608 while for dual patch-clamp and extracellular recordings the distance between the two craniotomies
609 was $\sim 2 \text{ mm}$ (Fig. 6, and Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 1-5).

610
611 For *in vivo* experiments in non-anesthetized head-restrained animals, 2 weeks before the recording
612 session mice were anesthetized with isoflurane 2.5% and a custom metal plate was fixed with
613 dental cement on the skull. After a 2-3 days recovery period, animals were habituated to sit quietly
614 on the experimental rig while their head was fixed. Habituation was performed for a minimum of 7-
615 10 days. One training session per day was performed and the duration of the training session
616 gradually increased each day (from 15 minutes to 1 hour). The day of the experiment, mice were
617 anesthetized with isoflurane 2.5% and a craniotomy was opened on the targeted area as described

618 above. After the surgery, mice recovered for at least 30 minutes before the beginning of the
619 experimental session.

620
621 *Simultaneous LFP and two-photon-guided juxtosomal recordings in vivo*

622 Double transgenic PV-Cre \times TdTomato and SST-Cre \times TdTomato mice were used for these
623 experiments. A low resistance (0.3 – 0.6 M Ω) pipette was filled with ACSF, lowered in the
624 craniotomy at \sim 300 μ m depth from the pial surface and used to monitor the superficial LFP
625 activity. A second glass pipette with higher resistance (5 – 8 M Ω) filled with ACSF and 2 mM
626 Alexa 488 Fluor (Thermo Fisher Scientific[®], Waltham, MA, USA) was used for juxtosomal
627 electrophysiological recordings. The second pipette was placed 80 – 350 μ m below the pial surface
628 and PV or SST positive interneurons were identified by imaging TdTomato fluorescence with an
629 Ultima II laser scanning two-photon microscope (Bruker Corp., Billerica, MA, former Prairie
630 Technologies, Madison, WI, USA) coupled to a Chameleon Ultra II (Coherent Corp., Santa Clara,
631 CA, λ_{exc} = 720 nm). When the tip of the pipette and the targeted cell were in close contact, a
632 negative pressure was applied to the pipette in order to achieve the juxtosomal recording
633 configuration (resistance > 20 M Ω). For LFP recordings, the electrical signal was amplified using
634 an AM-amplifier (AM-system, Carlsborg, WA, USA), digitized at 10 kHz and stored with
635 PatchMaster software (RRID:SCR_000034). Spiking activity from juxtosomal recordings was
636 acquired with an ELC-01X Amplifier, digitized (10 kHz) and stored with the same software as for
637 the LFP signal.

638
639 *Extracellular and intracellular recordings in vivo*

640 LFP and multi-unit activity (MUA) were acquired using custom-built probes made of two parallel
641 tungsten electrodes (FHC Inc., Bowdoin, ME, USA). The distance between the tips of the
642 electrodes was \sim 200 – 250 μ m. Electrodes were lowered into the tissue with the deeper tip placed
643 at \sim 350 μ m from pial surface. For simultaneous recordings of MUA (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement

644 1, 2, 5) in two cortical regions, two different probes were inserted in the same hemisphere 1.5 - 2
645 mm away from each other in the rostro-caudal direction and lowered at the same cortical depth.
646 Electrical signals were filtered at 0.1 Hz – 5 kHz, amplified by an AM-amplifier (AM-system,
647 Carlsborg, WA, USA) and digitized at 50 kHz with a Digidata 1440 (Axon Instruments, Union
648 City, CA).
649 Current-clamp patch-clamp recordings were carried out on superficial pyramidal neurons (100 –
650 350 μm). 3-6 M Ω borosilicate glass pipettes (Hilgenberg, Malsfeld, Germany) were filled with an
651 internal solution containing (in mM): K-gluconate 140, MgCl₂ 1, NaCl 8, Na₂ATP 2, Na₃GTP 0.5,
652 HEPES 10, Tris-phosphocreatine 10 to pH 7.2 with KOH. In some experiments byocitin (3 mg/ml)
653 was also added for post hoc cell identification and reconstruction. Electrical signals were acquired
654 using a Multiclamp 700B amplifier, filtered at 10 kHz, digitized at 50 kHz with a Digidata 1440 and
655 stored with pClamp 10 (RRID:SCR_011323, Axon Instruments, Union City, CA).

656

657 *Optical stimulation*

658 Continuous wave, solid-state laser sources (CNI, Changchun, China; World Star Tech, Toronto,
659 Canada; Cobolt, Vretenvägen, Sweden) were used to deliver blue ($\lambda = 473 \text{ nm}$, 488 nm or 491 nm,
660 stimulus duration 10 ms, unless otherwise stated) or yellow ($\lambda = 594 \text{ nm}$, stimulus duration 500 ms)
661 light illumination through an optical fiber (fiber diameter: 200 μm ; fiber numerical aperture: 0.22;
662 AMS Technologies, Milan, Italy) or, for patterned illumination experiments, via a 10X object
663 (Olympus, Tokyo, JP), coupled to a digital mirror device (DMD). Light power used for blue light
664 illumination ranged between 0.2 – 18 mW, while for yellow light between 0.12– 30 mW. Laser
665 power was measured at the fiber tip or underneath the objective. During *in vivo* recordings, the
666 optical fiber was placed in close proximity to the pial surface above the recording site.

667

668 For patterned illumination (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2), the beam was expanded by a first
669 telescope using achromatic doublet lenses (L_1 and L_2 in Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2a;

670 respectively AC254-035-A and AC254-150-A, Thorlabs, Dachau, DE) to impinge on the active
671 window of the DMD (V-7000 module, ViALUX Chemnitz, DE) with an angle of -24° with respect
672 to the direction normal to the DMD active window. The ON axis component of the modulated beam
673 (exiting at 0° with respect to the direction normal to the DMD active window) was then relayed by
674 a series of doublets lenses (L_3 , L_4 , L_5 in Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2a, respectively AC254-100-
675 A, AC254-060-A and AC254-100-A, Thorlabs) and a 10X microscope objective (UPlanFLN 10x
676 0.3NA, Olympus, Tokyo, JP) to the sample. Laser intensity was modulated by an acousto-optic
677 modulator (AOM, R23080-3-LTD, Gooch & Housego, Ilminster, UK) and neutral density filters
678 (NEK01, Thorlabs) positioned at the beam exit from the laser for experimental purposes. Before
679 entering the microscope objective the beam went through a dichroic mirror (Di01-R404/488/594,
680 Semrock, Rochester, NY, USA). Fluorescence emission was collected through a lens (L_6 , $f = 180$
681 mm, U-TLUIR, Olympus, Tokyo, JP) by a camera (ORCA-Flash4.0, Hamamatsu, Hamamatsu, JP)
682 with an appropriate emission filter in front of it. The DMD was controlled using custom-made
683 software written in LabVIEW (RRID:SCR_014325, National Instruments, Austin, TX), which
684 manage the communication with the ViALUX driving board using the ALP-4.1 controller suite.
685 The ALP-4.1 Advanced Programming Interface (API) allowed loading the patterns to an on-board
686 memory, setting triggers and stimulation time, and managing other driver functionalities.
687 Calibration was performed projecting a square pattern, adapting it to the pre-calibrated camera field
688 of view, and retrieving the mapping parameters between DMD and sample plane. In experiments
689 displayed in Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2, a circular shape (diameter: $200\ \mu\text{m}$) was projected
690 onto the surface of the brain close to one of the two recording electrodes (Ch1).

691
692 To measure the fraction of light transmitted through the brain tissue, the same optical fiber used for
693 *in vivo* experiments was placed perpendicularly to the slice (slice thickness: 0.05 - 1 mm) and in
694 close proximity to the tissue surface. Transmitted laser power was measured by placing the sensor
695 of the power meter underneath the cortical slice. The “transmission fraction” was calculated as the

696 ratio between the measured laser power in the presence of the cortical tissue and the maximal laser
697 power obtained in absence of the cortical slice (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 6b). The transmission
698 fraction was plotted as a function of the slice thickness and the scattering coefficient was obtained
699 from data interpolation as in (Aravanis et al., 2007).

700

701 The volume of tissue in which cells were efficiently modulated by light (0.0193 mm^3 for PV cells
702 and 0.159 mm^3 for SST interneurons) was calculated based on the diameter of the optical fiber (200
703 μm), the numerical aperture of the optical fiber (0.22), and the maximal depth at which interneurons
704 could be reliably modulated by light (320 μm for PV cells and 1 mm for SST interneurons). The
705 latter parameter was calculated from the equation displayed in Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 6c.
706 The minimal laser power (I_z) required to efficiently silence interneurons was evaluated in *in vitro*
707 recordings in coronal slices and corresponded to the laser power required to completely silence
708 interneurons during a step of current injection (150 – 750 pA) that elicited sustained firing activity.
709 I_z was $\sim 1.4 \text{ mW}$ and $\sim 0.5 \text{ mW}$ for PV and SST cells, respectively. For PV interneurons, $I_{z=0}$ (7.5
710 mW) was calculated as the minimal laser power value that, in inhibitory optogenetic experiments *in*
711 *vivo*, prolonged the up state, increased up state generation probability, and increased spiking activity
712 during up and down states. For SST cells, $I_{z=0}$ (16 mW) was calculated based only on the first two
713 parameters due to the absence increased spiking activity in pyramidal cells after photoinhibition of
714 SST interneurons.

715

716 *Slice electrophysiology*

717 Cortical slices were prepared as described previously (Beltramo et al., 2013). For patch-clamp
718 recordings pipettes (tip resistance, 3–4 M Ω) were filled with (in mM): K-gluconate 140, MgCl₂ 1,
719 NaCl 8, Na₂ATP 2, Na₃GTP 0.5, HEPES 10, Tris-phosphocreatine 10 to pH 7.2 with KOH.
720 Extracellular solution was: 125 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 1.25 NaH₂PO₄, 25 NaHCO₃, 2 MgCl₂, 2 CaCl₂, 25
721 glucose, pH 7.4 with 95 % O₂/5 % CO₂. Series resistance (range 6-20 M Ω) was not compensated and

722 data were not corrected for the liquid junction potential. The system for signal amplification,
723 digitalization and storage (Axon Instruments, Union City, CA) was the same used for intracellular
724 recordings *in vivo* (see above). For voltage-clamp experiments, the signal was sampled at 10 kHz
725 and filtered at 2 kHz.

726

727 *Immunohistochemistry, cell morphology reconstruction, and cell density measurement*

728 For immunofluorescence analysis, animals were deeply anesthetized with urethane (16,5%) and
729 transcardially perfused with 0.01 M PBS (pH 7.4) and 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS. Brains were
730 post-fixed overnight and cryoprotected with 30 % sucrose in PBS. Coronal slices (40 µm-thick)
731 were then cut and sequentially collected. Slices were incubated for 48 h at 4°C with primary
732 antibody diluted in PBS containing 5% normal serum of the same species as the secondary
733 antibody, 0.3% Triton-X 100 and 0.01% sodium azide, and then placed for 2-3 hours at room
734 temperature (RT) with the appropriate secondary antibody. Counterstain with Hoechst (1:400, 30
735 minutes RT) was performed before slices were mounted on glass slides with 1,4diazobicyclo-
736 (2,2,2)octane (DABCO)-based antifade mounting medium and finally coverslipped. The following
737 antibodies were used for the immunofluorescence procedures: anti-GABA (RRID:AB_477652,
738 1:100 rabbit, Sigma A2052); anti-parvalbumin (RRID:AB_477329, 1:1000 mouse, Sigma P3088);
739 anti-somatostatin (RRID:AB_2255365, 1:200 rat, Millipore MAB 354). Secondary antibodies
740 consisted of: goat anti-rabbit 488 (RRID:AB_2576217, 1:800, Invitrogen A11034), goat anti-rabbit
741 647 (RRID:AB_2535813, 1:800, Invitrogen A21245), goat anti-mouse 488 (RRID:AB_2534088,
742 1:800, Invitrogen A11029); goat anti-rat 647 (RRID:AB_141778, 1:800, Invitrogen A21247).
743 Confocal high-resolution images (2048 x 2048 pixels; Leica SP5, Wetzlar, DE) were used for cell
744 count analysis displayed in Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 1. Slices were randomly chosen in a rough
745 volume (~1.5 mm radius) around the injection site and cell count was restricted to the supragranular
746 layers of the cortex.

747

748 Biocytin-filled neurons were stained using the following protocol: coronal slices (250 μm) were
749 incubated for 20 minutes in 3% H_2O_2 containing PBS solution for peroxidase inactivation,
750 permeabilized for 1 hour RT with 2% Triton X-100 solution and subsequently kept overnight at 4°C
751 with the avidin-biotin HRP complex (ABC, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) solution
752 containing 1% Triton X-100. The day after, slices were washed with PBS and then incubated with
753 DAB (DAB Peroxidase Substrate Kit, 3, 3'-diaminobenzidine, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame,
754 CA, USA). The reaction was monitored under a stereomicroscope and stopped when labelled
755 neurons became visible. Slices were finally mounted with DABCO. Morphological reconstruction
756 was performed with Neurolucida (RRID:SCR_001775, MicroBrightField Williston, VT, USA).

757

758 To calculate opsin-positive cell density, PV-Cre or SST-Cre x TdTomato mice were injected with
759 ChR2. The cortical region was selected following ChR2 expression and TdTomato-positive cells
760 were counted using a systematic random sampling method applied to four consecutive sections per
761 animal. Sampling was performed by applying a virtual counting grid (square's size 80 x 80 μm)
762 over the whole area of interest using Neurolucida (Micro-BrightField, Colchester, VT, USA). Cells
763 were counted throughout the whole thickness of the slice (40 μm) counting sequentially in one out
764 of each four squares of the grid. Cells contacting a line on the upper or left edge of the grid element
765 were excluded and cells contacting the lower or right edge of the grid element were included in the
766 count. The number and position of each cell in the counted area were marked. Cell planar density
767 (number of labelled cells / mm^2) was calculated, and the total number (T) of labelled cells within a
768 given volume V was estimated as: $T = (N \times V) / t$, where N is the cell density and t the thickness of
769 the sections. The fraction of TdTomato-positive neurons which was also positive for ChR2 (ChR2-
770 eYFP/Tdtomato double-labelled cells) was evaluated on confocal z-stacks (1 μm steps; Leica SP5,
771 Wetzlar, DE) on the same sections and same cortical areas used for the measurement of the density
772 of TdTomato-positive cells. The percentage of double-labelled cells was used to finally estimate the
773 total number of opsin-expressing cells within the illuminated volume.

774

775 *Up and down state detection from LFP signal*

776 The raw LFP signal was first low-pass filtered below 500 Hz (second-order elliptic filter, 0.1 dB
777 peak-to-peak passband ripple, 40 dB stopband attenuation down from the peak passband value) and
778 then down-sampled to 1 kHz. Up and down states were then detected from the so-processed LFP
779 using a method based on combining the approach of Saleem and colleagues (Saleem et al., 2010)
780 (based on the instantaneous phase of the LFP in the low-frequency < 4 Hz band), with a modified
781 version of the algorithm proposed by Mukovski et al. (Mukovski et al., 2007) (exploiting
782 differences in beta and gamma-band power between up and down states). Since the Saleem method
783 depended on the choice of two low-frequency bands, whose instantaneous phase was used for state
784 detection, as well as on a few angular parameters that may vary according to the specific recording
785 configuration, we optimized these parameters for our experimental conditions by using six
786 simultaneous LFP and patch-clamp recordings on pyramidal neurons (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement
787 1). The MATLAB source code used to perform these calculations is available as a supplementary
788 material file (Source Code File 1). Up/down states were first detected from membrane potential
789 traces of pyramidal neurons (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1a) and those results were used as
790 ground-truth data to calibrate and estimate the performance of the up/down state detection from the
791 LFP signal (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1b). To detect up/down states, membrane potential traces
792 were analysed as proposed by (Saleem et al., 2010), with the only difference that we set the
793 minimum interval between consecutive states at 50 ms. To facilitate the comparison with the
794 method of (Saleem et al., 2010) we set the polarity of the LFP so that the “troughs” of the LFP
795 corresponded to up states and the peaks of the LFP to down states. We found that under our
796 conditions the optimal bands for state detection were [0-1 Hz] and [1-3 Hz], slightly different values
797 with respect to the optimal bands [0- 2 Hz] and [2-4 Hz] (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1f) found in
798 (Saleem et al., 2010). Moreover, to assess the possible effect of the method used to extract the
799 instantaneous LFP phase, we computed the phase either as the angle of the Hilbert transform or by

800 using linear interpolation between peaks/troughs and zero-crossing points (Eschenko et al., 2012).
801 We found that the phase computed by Hilbert transform gave better state detection performance,
802 thus we reported only results referring to states detected using Hilbert phase (Figure 1 - Figure
803 Supplement 1g).

804 The output of the Saleem method is a decision (or evidence) variable $S_{delta}(t)$, computed by
805 combining the differential likelihood of observing an up or down state from the chosen bands,
806 which varies between 0 and 1 and can be used to determine the instantaneous state. To also take
807 advantage of the information about the state given by higher frequencies, following (Mukovski et
808 al., 2007) we combined $S_{delta}(t)$ with another decision variable extracted from the LFP in the 10-
809 40 Hz range including the beta and gamma bands ($S_{beta-gamma}(t)$). We chose to use such band
810 because we noticed that in this frequency interval there are the highest differences between power
811 spectra as computed during either up or down states (Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1). To calculate
812 $S_{beta-gamma}(t)$, we first processed the filtered signal to accentuate the difference between the
813 periods of high-amplitude fluctuations and those of low amplitudes in the [10, 40] Hz band. To do
814 that, we calculated the standard deviation (corresponding to the root mean square) of the filtered
815 signal in a running frame of 5 ms. Then, we smoothed the obtained trace with a 50-ms running
816 frame linear filter (Mukovski et al., 2007). Finally, the resulting signal has been normalized
817 between 0 and 1, in order to be averaged with $S_{delta}(t)$ and obtain $S_{comb}(t)$ (Figure 1 - Figure
818 Supplement 1c). We show in Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1e that the performances obtained by
819 the algorithm when considering $S_{comb}(t)$ are slightly higher than when using $S_{delta}(t)$ alone;
820 hence, we decided to use $S_{comb}(t)$ instead of $S_{delta}(t)$ to estimate the state at each time instant.
821 To determine the thresholds for the detection of up/down states, the distribution of $S_{comb}(t)$ was
822 fitted by a mixture of three Gaussians using an expectation maximization algorithm (Saleem et al.,
823 2010). Each Gaussian represents a different cortical state, i.e. up (highest values of S_{comb}), down
824 (lowest), and indeterminate (intermediate). Time samples corresponding to $S_{comb}(t) > \mu_{UP} - 2\sigma_{UP}$

825 were assigned to up states, and samples corresponding to $S_{comb}(t) < \mu_{DOWN} + 2\sigma_{DOWN}$ to down
826 states (where means and variances of the Gaussians are represented as μ_{UP} , μ_{DOWN} , and σ_{UP} ,
827 σ_{DOWN} for the up and down cortical states, respectively). The remaining samples were considered
828 as indeterminate state. As done for the membrane potential, we set the minimum state duration
829 equal to 100 ms and the minimum inter-state interval equal to 50 ms. To assess the performance of
830 the algorithm, we computed Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC, Figure 1 - Figure Supplement
831 1e) curves for both up and down state detection: for up states, true positives are those time instants
832 defined as “up” on the basis of both membrane potential and LFP, whereas false positives are time
833 instants defined as “down” in the membrane potential, but classified as “up” from the LFP signal.
834 The analogous definitions were applied for down state detection.

835 To evaluate whether the number of spikes fired from interneurons during down states was
836 significantly higher than what could be predicted if all spikes came from misclassified time bins
837 (i.e. in which down states were falsely detected from the LFP), we implemented the following test.
838 We computed empirically from the ground truth data the probability that a time bin (20 ms
839 resolution) is wrongly classified as down state for each given value of S_{comb} . For each interneuron,
840 the overall probability that all its putative down-state spikes were fired in misclassified bins was
841 calculated taking the product over all spikes of down-state misclassification probability given the
842 corresponding S_{comb} value. Due to the rarity of down-state spikes, we assumed that the probability
843 of misclassifying a bin containing a spike is roughly independent of that of other bins. This allowed
844 us to compute the overall probability that all spikes come from misclassified bins as the product
845 over all bins containing spikes of single-bin misclassification. This number thus quantifies the
846 probability of the null hypothesis to be true (i.e. all interneurons’ spikes are fired in misclassified
847 bins, hence interneurons never fire during down state), and was considered as p-value for each
848 single interneuron.

849 All the analyses were performed by using custom-made software implemented in MATLAB
850 (RRID:SCR_001622, The Mathworks, Natick, MA, USA).

851

852 *Phase locking and causal analysis between PV/SST interneurons and LFP*

853 To investigate the temporal relationship between PV/SST interneurons' spiking activity and
854 up/down state occurrence during spontaneous activity, we asked whether the LFP slow oscillation
855 phase (which in turn reflects cortical state) is related to the occurrence of spikes in PV/SST
856 interneurons by quantifying the phase locking of spikes. To do that, we applied the method detailed
857 in (Eschenko et al., 2012) (Siapas et al., 2005). Briefly, we computed the instantaneous low-
858 frequency phase of the LFP as the angle of the Hilbert transform of the LFP trace filtered in the
859 [0.1, 4] Hz band. The phase-of-firing distribution quantifies, for each cell, the phase values at which
860 each spike was fired. Non-uniform phase-of-firing distributions mean that neurons fire
861 preferentially at certain phases. Hence, phase locking can be detected by assessing departure from
862 uniformity in the distribution of rescaled phases observed at spike times. To correct for the effect of
863 possible non-uniformities in the phase distributions due to asymmetries in the LFP wave shape
864 (Siapas et al., 2005), we made the overall distribution of phase across all time points uniform by
865 rescaling it by its cumulative distribution. The significance of phase locking was computed as
866 departure from uniformity of the phase of firing distribution, using the Rayleigh's test (Siapas et al.,
867 2005). To infer possible causal dependencies between spikes and phase time series, we also
868 computed how the phase locking between spike train and LFP ($p < 0.01$, Bonferroni corrected)
869 varies when the two signals are shifted in time with respect to the other. We computed the phase-
870 of-firing distribution for each shift value τ of the LFP trace with respect to the spike train between -
871 0.5 s and 0.5 s. For each of these distributions, we measured the strength of locking as one minus
872 the circular variance, to quantify the concentration of the distribution of angles (Eschenko et al.,
873 2012; Montemurro et al., 2008). To reliably estimate phase of firing distributions, we restricted the
874 analysis to those cells firing at least 100 spikes in the whole recording (16/16 for PV cells, 15/19 for
875 SST cells).

876 To estimate the temporal extent of the putative causation of interneurons on slow wave dynamics,
877 we considered the range of negative time shifts τ for which the time-shifted phase locking was both
878 statistically significant and, more conservatively, higher than the maximal value of time shifted
879 locking over $\tau \geq 0$: indeed, no locking value at $\tau \geq 0$, by definition, can capture any causal
880 relationships of spikes on slow waves (instead, locking values at $\tau \geq 0$ can be significant due to e.g.
881 the autocorrelation of the phase time series and the entrainment of spike to slow oscillations). These
882 putative causation time ranges have naturally the form $\tau_{\text{end}} \leq \tau < 0$ (for two PV cells where τ_{end} was
883 less than -0.5s we conservatively set $\tau_{\text{end}} = -0.5\text{s}$). For each cell, we further determined the time
884 shift corresponding to the maximum strength of locking (τ_{max}).

885 We also determined the preferred phase-of-firing at $\tau = 0$, $\tau = \tau_{\text{max}}$ and $\tau = \tau_{\text{end}}$, by calculating
886 the circular median of the phase of firing distribution. Moreover, for each cell we computed the
887 width of the phase of firing as its interquartile range. To estimate phase values associated to the start
888 and the end of up/down states we considered the statistical distributions of instantaneous phase at
889 state onset/offset detected from the LFP as reported in Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1h, i. We
890 determined the start or the end of the state as the phase value associated to the peak of the
891 distribution and we considered these values to determine the boundaries of up and down state
892 displayed in Fig. 2c, e, i, k. To better investigate the nature of the phase of firing distributions, we
893 computed the phase of firing histograms for each neuron in that state, and separately for up, down
894 and transition (down-to-up and up-to-down) states, in two different ways (Figure 2 - Figure
895 Supplement 1 and 2). The first quantification (phase of firing strength), that identifies the phase bins
896 in which more spikes are fired, computed in each phase bin the number of spikes per phase bin
897 averaged across all occurrences of a state. The second quantification (phase of firing reliability),
898 that identifies the phase bins in which spikes are discharged more reliably across the occurrences of
899 a state, computed in each phase bin the fraction of occurrences of a state in which we observed at
900 least one spike. The two quantifications, for each phase bin, coincide if a neuron fires one spike in

901 that phase bin. The two quantifications differ if a neuron fires sometimes more than one spike per
902 phase bin and this number varies across different occurrences of a state. The similarity between
903 phase of firing strength and phase of firing reliability (pooling up, down and transition states
904 together) was evaluated, separately for each neuron, as the Pearson correlation coefficient across
905 phase bins of the histograms of these two quantities. The population averaged Pearson correlation
906 was: 0.986 ± 0.004 for $N = 16$ PV cells, and 0.996 ± 0.001 for $N = 15$ SST cells, $p < 0.05$ for all
907 correlations calculated in individual cells.

908 Finally, to assess the nature of the changes in the spike-triggered LFP over the putative causal time
909 range, we looked for statistically detectable differences in the LFP phase speed (i.e. the rate of
910 change of the LFP phase) across the spike times, over timescales of the order of τ_{end} . More
911 specifically, we considered, separately for up and down states and for PV and SST interneuron
912 firing activity, all of the spikes occurring in a window between $-X$ and -200 ms before the end of
913 state (where X was varied parametrically between -400 and -300 ms). We included only data up
914 to -200 ms before end of state because this was the range of causation exerted by the interneuron's
915 firing on phase dynamics that we found in real data (see Results). To test whether there was a
916 difference between phase speed pre- and post-spike we computed, separately for each population of
917 interneurons and for up and down states, the time-average of the phase speed over a time window T
918 around the spike time (T varied between 50 and 200 ms). We then compared the pre- and post-spike
919 results with a t test. We checked that the results of these comparisons were consistent across the
920 different choices of the parameters X and T . Results of Fig. 2 and Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 3
921 were computed for $X = -400$ ms and $T = 200$ ms. To check that the results of the statistical tests are
922 not due to intrinsic asymmetries of the LFP dynamics close to state end, we repeated the same
923 comparisons with control data. For each data stretch of phase speed around a spike time included in
924 the analysis above, we selected a "control stretch" of LFP phase speed as follows: we first
925 computed the time average of the data stretch over the whole 400 ms interval centered on the
926 corresponding interneuron spike time, then we randomly chose an equally long control stretch

927 recorded when the interneuron was silent, whose distance from the respective state end was equal to
928 the distance of the data stretch from its state end, and whose time average over the respective whole
929 400 ms interval differed from the data stretch time-average by less than 50 deg/s. We then triggered
930 the phase speed change analysis to the centers of the control stretches rather than to the timings of a
931 spike, which are the centers of the data stretches.

932

933 *Analysis of in vivo intracellular recordings*

934 Recordings were inspected *a posteriori* to determine whether the optogenetic stimulus was
935 delivered during an up or during a down state. A stimulus was delivered during an up state if the
936 membrane potential of cell was stably depolarized (> 10 mV) over the resting potential of that cell
937 in a time window of 100 ms before the light stimulus. A stimulus was delivered during a down state
938 if the membrane potential of cell was stably within ± 3 mV from the resting potential of that cell in
939 a time window of 100 ms before the light stimulus. Trials which did not satisfy either criterion were
940 not considered for analysis. For photostimulation experiments in Fig. 3, 6 and Figure 6 - Figure
941 Supplement 4, the change in membrane voltage (Δ mV) was calculated in a time window before
942 (Pre, duration, 100 ms and 50 ms for experiments in anesthetized or non-anesthetized animals,
943 respectively) and after (Post, duration, 100 ms) light stimulation in 10 representative stimulation
944 trials per cell. In photoinhibition experiments in which the membrane potential was measured (Fig.
945 4, 6 and Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 4), three time windows were considered: Pre (duration, 100
946 ms and 50 ms for anesthetized or non-anesthetized experiments, respectively), Light (duration, 500
947 ms), and Post (duration, 100 ms). In photoinhibition experiments in which the spike frequency was
948 evaluated, longer time windows were considered: Pre (duration, 1 s), Light (duration, 500 ms), and
949 Post (duration, 1 s). In Fig. 5, only the recordings in which stimulation occurred during a down state
950 were considered. The onset of the optogenetically triggered up state was determined as the time at
951 which the cell membrane potential crossed a threshold set at 2 times the standard deviation of the
952 average down state membrane voltage value which was calculated in the Pre time window. The

953 standard deviation associated to the onset was evaluated for each single neuron and its average
954 across cells was used to estimate the temporal variation (jitter) for the triggered up state. To
955 evaluate the membrane potential speed in pyramidal neurons during up-to-down (Figure 3 - Figure
956 Supplement 3) and down-to-up (Figure 5 - Figure Supplement 1) state transitions, we performed a
957 linear regression of the membrane potential as a function of time during the transition (Sanchez-
958 Vives et al., 2010) and we considered its angular coefficient (i.e., the slope). To compare
959 optogenetically-evoked transitions with spontaneously occurring transitions, for each recorded cell
960 we manually selected ten evoked and ten spontaneous transitions and we evaluated the average
961 slope of selected transitions across cells. To estimate the time lag between the up-to-down or the
962 down-to-up transition in the experiments reported in figure 6 (Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 3), we
963 calculated the onset of each transition as the time at which the cell membrane potential crossed a
964 threshold set at two times the standard deviation of the average down, or up state membrane voltage
965 value calculated in the Pre time window. The difference between the onset of transition from the
966 cell recorded in channel 2 and the transition onset from the cell in channel 1 was considered as the
967 transition time lag (Ch2-Ch1 delay in Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 3).

968

969 *Analysis of in vivo extracellular recordings*

970 LFP and MUA signals were analysed with custom made software programmed in MATLAB.
971 Extracellular signals were inspected *a posteriori* to determine whether the optogenetic stimulus was
972 delivered during an up or during a down state, similarly to what done for intracellular recordings.
973 Up and down states were identified based on the presence of high frequency oscillations in the LFP
974 or the appearance of extracellular spikes in the MUA. LFP traces were downsampled by a factor of
975 50 (from 50 kHz to 1 kHz) and low-pass filtered using a Chebyshev Type I filter (corner frequency,
976 100 Hz). The frequency content of the LFP was evaluated with spectrograms computed using 100-
977 ms Hamming windows shifted every 1 ms. The one-sided modified periodogram estimate of the

978 power spectral density (PSD) was computed (FFT length: 500 points) for each window and plotted
979 as a function of time and frequency (0-100 Hz) in a logarithmic scale. A blanking window of 10 ms
980 at the beginning of the Pre and Post windows was used to exclude stimulation artefacts. The relative
981 power in the low gamma (30-60 Hz) and high gamma (60-90 Hz) range was computed by
982 integrating the PSD function over the two frequency ranges and normalizing the integral over the
983 total signal power in the pre-stimulus window. The PSD is estimated by means of the Welch's
984 averaged modified periodogram spectral estimation method (segment length: half of the considered
985 window; overlap: 50%) (Welch, 1967).

986 The MUA signal was isolated by high-pass filtering (corner frequency, 300 Hz). Spikes were
987 identified based on a threshold set at five times the standard deviation of the noise. 100 ms time
988 binning (10 ms for the dual MUA recordings) was used to compute spike count histograms. Spike
989 frequency was obtained as the total number of identified spikes in the different windows (Pre,
990 Light, and Post) over the temporal duration of the window. The MATLAB source code used to
991 perform these calculations is available as a supplementary material file (Source Code File 2).

992

993 *Study design and statistics*

994 For each experimental group, sample size was chosen based on previous *in vivo* studies (Beltramo
995 et al., 2013). No statistical methods were used to predetermine sample size. All recordings with no
996 technical issues were included in the analysis. Values are expressed as mean \pm s.e.m, unless
997 otherwise stated. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was run on each experimental sample to test for
998 normality. Two-tailed (unless otherwise stated) Student's *t*-test (in case of normal distribution), and
999 the Mann-Whitney or Wilcoxon signed-rank (for unpaired and paired comparison of non-normal
1000 distributed data, respectively) tests were used when comparing two populations. For comparison of
1001 more than two populations, one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni *post-hoc* test was used for normally
1002 distributed data; otherwise, the non-parametric Friedman with Dunn *post-hoc* test was applied.

1003 Statistical analysis was performed using OriginLAB (RRID:SCR_002815), GraphPad Prism
1004 (RRID:SCR_002798), or MATLAB (RRID:SCR_001622) software.

1005

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1012

1013 **Competing financial interests**

1014 The authors declare no competing financial interests.

1015

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Figure 1

1205

1206 **Figure 1. Firing activity of PV and SST interneurons during cortical up and down states *in***
 1207 ***vivo*.** **a)** Fluorescence image showing a glass pipette (dotted white line) used for juxtасomal
 1208 recordings from a PV positive interneuron (red cell) in a PV \times TdTomato bigenic transgenic animal.
 1209 **b)** Representative traces of simultaneous LFP (top) and juxtасomal (bottom) recordings from an
 1210 identified PV interneuron during up and down states. Pink and purple colours in the background
 1211 indicate up and down states that were identified from the LFP signal, respectively. The white
 1212 background colour indicates indeterminate states (see Materials and Methods). **c)** Action potentials
 1213 fired by PV cells in the three identified periods (up, down and indeterminate, $p = 7E-8$, one-way
 1214 ANOVA, $N = 16$ cells from 5 animals). In this as well in other figures: grey dots and lines indicate
 1215 single experiment; black dots and lines indicate the average value represented as mean \pm s.e.m; n.s.,
 1216 $p > 0.05$; *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$. **d)** Percentage of active up states and active down
 1217 states ($p = 3E-16$, unpaired Student's t -test, $N = 16$ cells from 5 animals). **e)** Number of spikes fired

1218 by PV cells per single up or down state ($p = 8E-6$, Mann-Whitney test, $N = 16$ cells from 5
1219 animals). **f-g)** Same as in a, b but in SSTxTdTomato bigenic transgenic animals. **h-j)** Same as in c-e
1220 for SST interneurons. In h, $p = 2E-8$, Friedman test, $N = 19$ cells from 7 animals. In i, $p = 1E-7$,
1221 Mann-Whitney test, $N = 19$ cells from 7 animals. In j, $p = 9E-3$, Mann-Whitney test, $N = 19$ cells
1222 from 7 animals.

1223 **Figure 1 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of the firing activity of PV and SST**
1224 **interneurons during up and down states.**

1225 **Source Code File 1: UP/DOWN state detection on LFP recordings and quantification of**
1226 **inhibitory interneurons firing properties.** Functions and scripts contained in this file have been
1227 used to produce data and plots reported in Figure 1 and Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1.

1228

Figure 2

1230

1231 **Figure 2: Temporal correlation between the activity of PV and SST interneurons and the**

1232 **LFP. a) Schematic representation of the experimental configuration for simultaneous LFP**

1233 **recording and fluorescence targeted juxtosomal recordings from PV interneurons. b) Phase of firing**

1234 **distribution of one representative PV interneuron in the absence of temporal shift ($\tau = 0$). The**

1235 **dashed line indicates the median. The shaded area indicates the range of preferred phase of firing**

1236 **defined as between the 25th and the 75th percentile. c) The horizontal grey lines indicate the range of**

1237 **preferred phase of firing for each recorded cell. The blue lines plot a cosine function used to show**

1238 **the phase convention in terms of LFP peaks and troughs. The crossing between each grey line and**

1239 **the blue sinusoid occurs at the median value of phase of firing for each recorded cell. The black line**

1240 **represents the values of the cell shown in b. Pink and purple regions indicate phase ranges**

1241 **belonging to up states and down states, respectively. d) Locking strength as a function of the time**

1242 shift τ for the representative PV interneuron displayed in b. The grey asterisk indicates the locking
1243 strength corresponding to the $\tau = 0$ value, the green asterisk that corresponding to the τ_{\max} value and
1244 the red asterisk that corresponding to the τ_{end} value. **e)** Same as in c but in presence of temporal shift
1245 $\tau = \tau_{\max}$ (left panel) and $\tau = \tau_{\text{end}}$ (right panel). **f)** LFP phase speed averaged over 200 ms before any
1246 PV interneuron spike lying between -400 ms and -200 ms from a state end and the LFP phase speed
1247 averaged over 200 ms after the same spikes. The post-spike phase speed is significantly higher than
1248 the pre-spike phase speed in up states (top panel), while it is significantly smaller in down states
1249 (bottom panel, for up states, $p = 2\text{E-}13$, one-tailed paired Student's t -test, $N = 8911$ stretches from
1250 16 cells; for down state, $p = 8\text{E-}3$, one-tailed paired Student's t -test, $N = 199$ stretches from 11
1251 cells). **g-k)** Same as in a-e but for SST interneurons. **l)** Spike-triggered phase speed analysis of SST
1252 interneurons as in f: the post-spike phase speed is significantly larger than the pre-spike phase speed
1253 in up states (top panel, $p = 2\text{E-}5$, one-tailed paired Student's t -test, $N = 1346$ stretches from 15
1254 cells), while there is no significant difference between the post-spike and the pre-spike phase speed
1255 in down states (bottom panel, $p = 0.6$, one-tailed paired Student's t -test, $N = 12$ stretches from 7
1256 cells).

1257 **Figure 2 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of the preferred phase of firing for PV**
1258 **and SST interneurons.**

1259 **Figure 2 – Source Data 2: Source data for the analysis of the spike triggered phase speed**
1260 **velocity.**

1261

1262

Figure 3

1264

1265 **Figure 3. Optogenetic activation of PV and SST interneurons triggers up-to-down transitions.**

1266 a) Top: schematic of the experimental configuration. ChR2 is expressed in PV cells (blue round

1267 circle) and intracellular recordings are performed from pyramidal neurons (grey triangle). Bottom:

1268 morphological reconstruction of one recorded layer II/III pyramidal neuron. b) Representative

1269 intracellular recordings showing the effect of PV interneuron activation when light (blue line) was

1270 delivered during an ongoing up state. Ten different trials are shown (one in black and the other in

1271 grey). c) Change in the membrane potential of recorded cells (ΔmV) before (Pre) and after (Post)

1272 PV interneuron activation during an ongoing up state in anesthetized (left) and non-anesthetized

1273 (right) mice. Left, $p = 7E-8$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 12$ cells from 7 animals; right, $p = 5E-4$,
1274 paired Student's t -test, $N = 6$ cells from 3 animals. **d-e)** Same as in b-c but for PV activation during
1275 ongoing down states. In e: left, $p = 5E-1$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 12$ cells 7 animals; right, $p = 7$
1276 $E-2$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 6$ cells from 3 animals. **f-j)** Same as in a-e but for photoactivation
1277 of SST interneurons. In h: left, $p = 1E-8$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 9$ cells from 6 animals; right, p
1278 $= 3E-2$, Wilcoxon signed rank test, $N = 6$ cells from 3 animals. In j: left, $p = 2E-1$, paired Student's
1279 t -test, $N = 9$ cells from 6 animals; right, $p = 2E-1$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 6$ cells from 3
1280 animals.

1281 **Figure 3 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of membrane potential changes during**
1282 **photostimulation of PV or SST interneurons.**

Figure 4

1284

1285 **Figure 4. Optogenetic inhibition of PV and SST cells prolongs the up state and triggers down-**
 1286 **to-up transitions. a)** Top: schematic of the experimental configuration. Bottom: morphological
 1287 reconstruction of a representative recorded neuron. **b)** Representative recordings from a pyramidal
 1288 cell during optogenetic inhibition (yellow line) of PV interneurons during an up state. **c)** Change in
 1289 the membrane potential (ΔmV) of recorded neurons before (Pre), during (Light), and after (Post)
 1290 optogenetic suppression of PV cells in anesthetized (left) and non-anesthetized (right) mice. Left: p
 1291 = 3E-8, one-way ANOVA, N = 11 cells from 4 animals; right: p = 2E-8, one-way ANOVA, N = 10
 1292 cells from 4 animals. **d-e)** Same as in b-c but for PV suppression during ongoing down states. In e:
 1293 left, p = 7E-8, one-way ANOVA, N = 11 cells from 4 animals; right, p = 2E-6, one-way ANOVA,

1294 N = 8 cells from 4 animals. **f-j)** Same as in a-e but for optogenetic inhibition of SST interneurons.
1295 In h: left, $p = 1E-6$, one-way ANOVA, N = 9 cells from 5 animals; right, $p = 7E-7$, one-way
1296 ANOVA, N = 8 cells from 5 animals. In j: left, $p = 1E-6$, one-way ANOVA, N = 9 cells from 5
1297 animals; right, $p = 2E-5$, one-way ANOVA, N = 8 cells from 5 animals.

1298 **Figure 4 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of membrane potential changes during**
1299 **photoinhibition of PV or SST interneurons.**

1301

1302 **Figure 5. Interneuron type-specific effect of optogenetic inhibitory manipulations. a)**

1303 Schematic of the experimental configuration where PV cells were photoinhibited. **b)** Firing rate of

1304 pyramidal neurons before (Pre), during (Light), and after (Post) PV photoinhibition during up (left)

1305 or down (right) state in anesthetized mice. Left: $p = 2E-4$, Friedman test, $N = 11$ cells from 4

1306 animals; right: $p = 1E-3$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 11$ cells from 4 animals. **c)** Distribution of the

1307 latency of the down-to-up state transition triggered by photoinhibition of PV cells during an

1308 ongoing down state in anesthetized mice. **d-e)** Same as in b-c but in non-anesthetized mice. In d:

1309 left, $p = 2E-4$, Friedman test, $N = 10$ cells from 4 animals; right, $p = 3E-4$, Friedman test, $N = 8$

1310 cells from 4 animals. **f)** Schematic of the experimental configuration where SST interneurons were

1311 photoinhibited. **g)** Same as in b but during photoinhibition of SST interneurons. Left: $p = 6E-1$,

1312 Friedman test, $N = 9$ cells from 5 animals; right: $p = 2E-1$, Friedman test, $N = 9$ cells from 5

1313 animals. **h)** Distribution of the latency of the down-to-up state transition triggered by

1314 photoinhibition of SST during an ongoing down state in anesthetized mice. **i-j)** Same as in g-h but

1315 in non-anesthetized mice. In i: left, $p = 7E-1$, Friedman test, $N = 8$ cells from 5 animals; right, $p =$

1316 $5E-1$, Friedman test, $N = 8$ cells from 5 animals.

1317 **Figure 5 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of the interneuron type-specific effect**
1318 **of optogenetic inhibitory manipulations.**

Figure 6

1320

1321 **Figure 6. Local modulation of cortical interneurons causes large-scale state transitions. a)**
 1322 Schematic representation of the experimental configuration. Simultaneous dual patch-clamp
 1323 recordings were performed in anesthetized mice during photoactivation of PV interneurons
 1324 expressing ChR2: Ch1 (red) indicates the recording site located close to the illuminated area,

1325 whereas Ch2 (green) represents the recording site placed 2 mm away from Ch1 in the caudal
1326 direction. **b)** Representative traces of two simultaneously recorded neurons (top, Ch1, red trace;
1327 bottom, Ch2 green trace) during photoactivation of PV interneurons. Bold red (Ch1) and green
1328 (Ch2) lines show a single representative trial. **c)** Change in the membrane potential (ΔmV) of
1329 recorded neurons before (Pre) and after (Post) PV activation during an ongoing up state. Grey dots
1330 and lines indicate single experiments, red (Ch1) or green (Ch2) dots and lines indicate the average
1331 value represented as mean \pm s.e.m. Top: $p = 7E-6$, paired Student's *t*-test, $N = 7$ cells from 3
1332 animals; bottom: $p = 6E-4$, paired Student's *t*-test, $N = 7$ cells from 3 animals. **d)** Schematic of the
1333 experimental configuration for dual patch-clamp recordings during photoinhibition of PV
1334 interneurons. **e)** Representative traces from two simultaneously recorded neurons (Ch1, red; Ch2,
1335 green) when photoinhibition of PV interneurons occurred during cortical down states. **f)** Change in
1336 the membrane potential (ΔmV) of recorded neurons before (Pre), during (Light), and after (Post)
1337 photoinhibition of PV cells. Top: $p = 4E-4$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 6$ cells from 4 animals; bottom:
1338 $p = 4E-5$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 6$ cells from 4 animals. **g)** Schematic representation of the
1339 experimental configuration for dual-patch clamp recording in mice expressing ChR2 in SST
1340 interneurons. **h-i)** Same as in b-c but during photoactivation of SST interneurons. In i: top, $p = 8E-$
1341 3 , Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 8$ cells from 6 animals; bottom, $p = 7E-6$, paired Student's *t*-test,
1342 $N = 8$ cells from 6 animals. **j)** Schematic representation of the experimental configuration for paired
1343 patch-clamp recording in mice expressing Arch in SST interneurons. **k-l)** Same as in h-i but
1344 inhibiting SST interneurons. In l: top, $p = 3E-5$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 7$ cells from 4 animals;
1345 bottom, $p = 1E-4$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 7$ cells from 4 animals.

1346 **Figure 6 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of membrane potential changes in**
1347 **simultaneously recorded neurons during local optogenetic perturbation of PV and SST**
1348 **interneurons.**

Figure 1 - Figure Supplement 1

1352 **Figure 1 – Figure Supplement 1. Up and down state detection from the LFP signal. a-c)** Representative
1353 example of up/down state detection results. Up/down state periods (pink and purple shadows, respectively)
1354 as detected from membrane potential are shown in a, whereas states detected in the LFP signal (and based on
1355 the decision variable trace shown in c) are reported in b. In c, the up state threshold is marked by the dotted
1356 pink line, whereas the down state threshold by the purple dotted line. **d)** Ratio between power spectral
1357 densities (PSD) of LFP in up/down states (representative cell in upper panel, mean \pm s.d. of all cells in lower
1358 panel). The light blue square indicates the 10-40 Hz range used in our algorithm. **e-g)** ROC curves for the
1359 detection of up (pink) and down (purple) states using either S_{delta} or S_{comb} are reported in e (representative
1360 cell). Up/down state ROC curves are shown either in the top left or in the bottom right half of the xy plane,
1361 respectively. The area under ROC curve (AUC) using different frequency bands for the computation of S_{delta}
1362 is shown in f. The AUC for the various metrics (i.e. S_{delta} or S_{comb}) or phase computation methods (i.e. Hilbert
1363 transform or interpolation) are shown in g. Red rectangles highlight the combinations of parameters giving
1364 the maximum performance. **h-i)** Statistical distributions of instantaneous phase during up/down states (up in
1365 h, down in i, black curves), state onset (in green), and state offsets (in red). Upper panels refer to state
1366 detection based on membrane potential, lower panels to state detection based on LFP. **j)** True positive (TPR)
1367 and false positive rates (FPR) obtained by detecting up/down states on S_{comb} traces ([0, 1]-[1, 3] Hz
1368 frequency bands, instantaneous phase computed by Hilbert transform).

1369 **Figure 1 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source data 1: Source data for Up and Down state detection**
1370 **from the LFP signal.**

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1374 **Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 1. Phase of firing strength and phase of firing reliability in PV**1375 **interneurons. a)** Histogram of the phase of firing strength (left) and histogram of the phase of

1376 firing reliability (right) for the representative PV interneuron showed in Figure 2b. Only spikes

1377 occurring during up states were considered. **b-d)** Same as in (a) for spikes fired during down states

1378 (b), up-to-down transitions (c) and down-to-up transitions (d).

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1381 **Figure 2 – Figure Supplement 2. Phase of firing strength and phase of firing reliability in SST**
 1382 **interneurons. a)** Histogram of the phase of firing strength (left) and histogram of the phase of
 1383 firing reliability (right) for the representative SST interneuron showed in Figure 2h. Only spikes
 1384 occurring during up states were considered. **b-d)** Same as in (a) for spikes fired during down states
 1385 (b), up-to-down transitions (c) and down-to-up transitions (d).

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Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 3

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Figure 2 – Figure Supplement 3. Spike-triggered phase speed across the times of interneuron spikes

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close to state end. a) Phase speed of the recorded LFP (mean \pm s.e.m.) triggered on a PV interneuron spike

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that was fired between 400 and 200 ms before the end of an up state, as a function of time. The spikes were

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selected with the only criterion that the entire stretch of considered phase speed lays within the same up state.

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b) Same as in a, but the phase speed corresponds to down states. **c-d)** as in a-b, but the analysed phase speed

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was triggered on SST interneuron spikes.

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1397 **Figure 2 - Figure Supplement 4. Correlation between LFP phase speed changes and firing**
 1398 **properties of cortical interneurons. a)** Plots of the LFP phase speed changes triggered by spikes
 1399 close to the end of up states as a function of the circular variance of the phases of firing
 1400 distributions in up states for PV (left) and SST (right) interneurons. Each dot represents one
 1401 recorded cell. In this as well as in the other panels, only cells with at least ten data stretches (see
 1402 Materials and Methods) in the up state were considered. **b)** LFP phase speed changes triggered by
 1403 spikes close to the end of up states as a function of the preferred phase of firing in up states of PV
 1404 (left) and SST (right) cells. **c)** Correlation plots between the preferred phase of firing for PV (left)

1405 and SST (right) interneurons and the circular variance of the phases of firing distributions in up
1406 states.

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1409 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 1. Immunohistochemical analysis of ChR2 positive cells in PV- and SST-**
 1410 **Cre animals. a-d)** Confocal images of coronal cortical sections from a PV-Cre animal injected with AAV
 1411 transducing ChR2-mCherry. ChR2 positive cells (shown in a) largely stain for GABA (shown in b). ChR2-
 1412 mCherry and GABA stainings are shown merged in c and the zoom of the region within the white square box
 1413 is reported in d. **e)** Total number of ChR2-positive, GABA-positive and ChR2 and GABA-positive neurons
 1414 in PV-Cre injected mice (N = 4 animals, 3 sections per animal). **f-i)** Same as in a-d but with a fluorescence
 1415 immunostaining for parvalbumin. **j)** Same as in e but for immunostaining for parvalbumin positive neurons
 1416 (N = 4 animals, 3 sections per animal). **k-t)** Same as in a-j but for SST-Cre animal injected with AAV
 1417 transducing ChR2-mCherry. In o, N = 4 animals, 3 sections per animal. In t, N = 4 animals, 3 sections per
 1418 animal.

1419 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source Data 1: Source data for the immunohistochemical**
1420 **analysis of ChR2 positive cells in PV-Cre and SST-Cre injected mice.**

1423 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 2. Functional analysis of PV and SST positive cells expressing ChR2. a-**
 1424 **b)** Confocal images of one coronal cortical section showing the expression of ChR2-mCherry in PV-Cre
 1425 mice. Cells are shown at an expanded time scale in b. c) Representative current-clamp patch-clamp
 1426 recordings in slices, showing the typical firing pattern of a PV cell positive for ChR2. d) Left: schematic
 1427 configuration for intracellular recordings from PV interneurons expressing ChR2 in coronal slices. Right:
 1428 membrane depolarization and action potential (AP) firing in response to a 10 ms pulse of light. e) Number of
 1429 APs fired as a function of the light intensity (N = 5 cells from 2 animals). f) Voltage-clamp patch-clamp
 1430 recording showing the photocurrent evoked in response to 300 ms of light stimulus. g) Quantification of the
 1431 total amount of net charge passing through the cell membrane as a function of the light intensity (N = 3 cells

1432 from 2 animals). **h-n)** Same as in a-g but for SST cells positive for ChR2. In 1, N = 9 cells from 3 animals. In
1433 n, N = 5 cells from 2 animals.

1434 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 2 – Source Data 1: Source data for the functional**
1435 **characterization of PV and SST interneurons expressing ChR2.**

Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 3

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1438 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 3. Membrane potential speed in pyramidal neurons during**
 1439 **optogenetically-evoked and spontaneous up-to-down state transitions. a)** Schematic of the
 1440 experimental configuration. **b)** Representative intracellular recording showing an up-to-down state
 1441 transition evoked by optogenetic activation (blue bar) of PV interneurons (top) or spontaneously
 1442 occurring (bottom). A linear fit (red line) was used to evaluate membrane potential speed during the
 1443 transition. **c)** Average membrane potential speed in pyramidal neurons during optogenetically-
 1444 triggered and spontaneous up-to-down state transitions (paired Student's *t*-test, $N = 12$ cells from 7
 1445 animals, $p = 2E-3$). **d-f)** Same as in a-c but for optogenetic activation of SST interneurons (evoked
 1446 vs spontaneous, paired Student's *t*-test, $N = 9$ cells from 6 animals, $p = 5E-4$). The slope of
 1447 optogenetically-evoked transitions was not significantly different when SST and PV cells were
 1448 stimulated (SST vs PV, Student's *t*-test, $N = 9$ cells and $N = 12$ respectively, $p = 4E-1$).

1449 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 3 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of membrane**
1450 **potential speed during optogenetically-evoked and spontaneous up-to-down state transitions.**

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Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4

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1455 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4. *In vivo* extracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1456 **photostimulation of PV positive interneurons expressing ChR2. a)** Representative trace of an *in vivo* LFP
 1457 recording (top) and corresponding spectrogram (bottom) showing the effect of optogenetic activation of PV
 1458 interneurons during an ongoing up state. The schematic of the experimental configuration is shown in the
 1459 inset (top panel). **b-c)** Average power in the 30 – 60 (b) and 60 – 90 (c) Hz frequency band before (Pre), and

1460 after (Post) light stimulation. Power values are normalized to the total power in the “Pre” time window. In b,
1461 $p = 2E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 13$ animals. In c, $p = 4E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 13$
1462 animals. **d)** Top: multi-unit signal corresponding to the trace showed in a. Bottom: peri-stimulus time
1463 histogram (PSTH) of the trace showed in the top panel. **e)** Average firing frequency of spikes (Hz) recorded
1464 in the multi-unit signal before (Pre) and after (Post) light stimulus ($p = 2E-4$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N =$
1465 13 animals). **f-j)** Same as in a-e but for optogenetic activation of PV interneurons during an ongoing down
1466 state. In g, $p = 5E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 13$ animals. In h, $p = 5E-2$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test,
1467 $N = 13$ animals. In j, $p = 3E-1$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 13$ animals.

1468 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 4 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of PV**
1469 **photoactivation during up states on network activity.**

1470 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 4 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of PV**
1471 **photoactivation during down states on network activity.**

1472 **Source Code File 2: Analysis of LFP and MUA recordings during optogenetic manipulation of**
1473 **interneurons.** Functions and scripts contained in this file have been used to produce data and plots
1474 reported in Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 4, 5 and Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3, 4.

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1478 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 5. *In vivo* extracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1479 **photostimulation of SST positive interneurons expressing ChR2. a) Representative trace of an *in vivo***
 1480 **LFP recording (top) and corresponding spectrogram (bottom) showing the effect of optogenetic activation of**

1481 SST interneurons expressing ChR2 during an ongoing up state. The schematic of the experimental
1482 configuration is shown in the inset (top panel). **b-c)** Average power in the 30 – 60 (b) and 60 – 90 (c) Hz
1483 frequency band before (Pre), and after (Post) light stimulation. Power values are normalized to the total
1484 power in the “pre” time window. In b, $p = 4E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals. In c, $p = 9E-3$,
1485 Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals. **d)** Multi-unit signal (top) and corresponding PSTH (bottom)
1486 related to the trace showed in a. **e)** Average firing frequency of spikes (Hz) recorded in the multi-unit signal
1487 before (Pre) and after (Post) light stimulus ($p = 2E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals). **f-j)** Same
1488 as in a-e but for optogenetic activation of SST interneurons during an ongoing down state. In g, $p = 8E-3$,
1489 Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals. In h, $p = 6E-1$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals. In j,
1490 $p = 1E-1$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $N = 10$ animals.

1491 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 5 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of SST**
1492 **photoactivation during up states on network activity.**

1493 **Figure 3 – Figure Supplement 5 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of SST**
1494 **photoactivation during down states on network activity.**

Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 6

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1497 **Figure 3 - Figure Supplement 6. *In vivo* intracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1498 **photostimulation of PV or SST positive interneurons in non-anesthetized animals. a)** Top: schematic of
 1499 the experimental configuration. Bottom: morphological reconstruction of a recorded layer II/III pyramidal
 1500 neuron. **b)** Representative intracellular recordings showing the effect of PV interneuron activation on the
 1501 membrane potential of the recorded pyramidal neuron when light (blue line) was delivered during ongoing
 1502 up states in a non-anesthetized mouse. **c)** Same as in b but for photoactivation of PV interneurons during
 1503 down states. **d-f)** Same as in a-c but in mice expressing ChR2 in SST interneurons.

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1507 **Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 1. Functional analysis of PV and SST positive cells expressing Arch. a-b)**

1508 Confocal images of coronal cortical sections showing the expression of Arch-eYFP in PV-Cre mice. **c)**

1509 Representative current-clamp patch-clamp recordings in slices, showing the typical firing pattern of a PV cell

1510 that was also positive for Arch. **d)** Left: schematic of the experimental configuration. Right: membrane

1511 potential response to 500 ms of light stimulation. AP discharge was induced by current injection. **e)**

1512 Quantification of the average firing frequency before (Pre), during (Light), and after (Post) light stimulation

1513 ($p = 9E-6$, Friedman test, $N = 13$ cells from 4 animals). **f-j)** Same as in a-e but for SST positive interneurons

1514 that express Arch. In j, $p = 2E-5$, Friedman test, $N = 13$ cells from 6 animals.

1515 **Figure 4 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source Data 1: Source data for functional characterization**
1516 **of PV and SST interneurons expressing Arch.**

Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 2

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1519 **Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 2. *In vivo* intracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1520 **photoinhibition of PV or SST positive interneurons in non-anesthetized animals. a)** Top: schematic
 1521 representation of the experimental configuration. Bottom: morphological reconstruction of a recorded layer
 1522 II/III pyramidal neuron. **b)** Representative intracellular recordings showing the effect of the optogenetic
 1523 inhibition of PV interneurons on the membrane potential of the recorded pyramidal neuron when light
 1524 (yellow line and shadow) was delivered during up states in a non-anesthetized mouse. **c)** Same as in b but for
 1525 optogenetic inhibition of PV interneurons during down states. **d-f)** Same as in a-c but in mice expressing
 1526 Arch in SST interneurons.

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1530 **Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 3. *In vivo* extracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1531 **photoinhibition of PV positive interneurons expressing Arch. a)** Representative trace of an *in vivo* LFP
 1532 recording (top) and corresponding spectrogram (bottom) showing the effect of optogenetic stimulation
 1533 (yellow line) of PV interneurons expressing Arch during an ongoing up state. The schematic of the
 1534 experimental configuration is shown in the inset (top panel). **b-c)** Average power in the 30 – 60 (b) and 60 –

1535 90 (c) Hz frequency band before (Pre), during (Light) and after (Post) light stimulation. Power values are
1536 normalized to the total power in the “pre” time window. In b, $p = 1E-7$, Friedman test, $N = 19$ animals. In c,
1537 $p = 9E-9$, Friedman test, $N = 19$ animals. **d)** Multi-unit signal (top) and corresponding PSTH (bottom) related
1538 to the trace showed in a. **e)** Average firing frequency of spikes (Hz) recorded in the multiunit signal before
1539 (Pre), during (light), and after (Post) light stimulus ($p = 1E-7$, one-way ANOVA, $N = 19$ animals). **f-j)** Same
1540 as in a-e but for photoinhibition of PV positive interneurons during an ongoing down state. In g, $p = 1E-8$,
1541 Friedman test, $N = 19$ animals. In h, $p = 2E-8$, Friedman test, $N = 19$ animals. In j, $p = 3E-8$, Friedman test,
1542 $N = 19$ animals.

1543 **Figure 4 – Figure Supplement 3 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of PV**
1544 **photoinhibition during up states on network activity.**

1545 **Figure 4 – Figure Supplement 3 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of PV**
1546 **photoinhibition during down states on network activity.**

Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4

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1549 **Figure 4 - Figure Supplement 4. *In vivo* extracellular recordings of spontaneous cortical dynamics and**
 1550 **photoinhibition of SST positive interneurons expressing Arch. a)** Representative trace of an *in vivo* LFP
 1551 recording (top) and corresponding spectrogram (bottom) showing the effect of optogenetic stimulation
 1552 (yellow line) of SST interneurons expressing Arch during an ongoing up state. The schematic of the

1553 experimental configuration is shown in the inset (top panel). **b-c)** Average power in the 30 – 60 (b) and 60 –
1554 90 (c) Hz frequency band before (Pre), during (Light), and after (Post) light stimulation. In b, $p = 3E-7$,
1555 Friedman test, $N = 18$ animals. In c, $p = 3E-6$, Friedman test, $N = 18$ animals. **d)** Multi-unit signal (top) and
1556 corresponding PSTH (bottom) related to the trace showed in a. **e)** Average firing frequency of spikes (Hz)
1557 recorded in the multi-unit signal before (Pre), during (light), and after (Post) light stimulus ($p = 4E-6$,
1558 Friedman test, $N = 18$ animals). **f-j)** Same as in a-e but for optogenetic inhibition of SST interneurons during
1559 an ongoing down state. In g, $p = 1E-6$, Friedman test, $N = 18$ animals. In h, $p = 3E-7$, Friedman test, $N = 18$
1560 animals. In j, $p = 3E-7$, Friedman test, $N = 18$ animals.

1561 **Figure 4 – Figure Supplement 4 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of SST**
1562 **photoinhibition during up states on network activity.**

1563 **Figure 4 – Figure Supplement 4 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of SST**
1564 **photoinhibition during down states on network activity.**

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Figure 5 - Figure Supplement 1

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1568 **Figure 5 - Figure Supplement 1. Membrane potential speed in pyramidal neurons during**
 1569 **optogenetically-evoked and spontaneous down-to-up state transitions.** a) Schematic of the
 1570 experimental configuration. b) Representative intracellular recording showing a down-to-up state
 1571 transition evoked by optogenetic inhibition (yellow bar) of PV interneurons (top) or spontaneously
 1572 occurring (bottom). A linear fit (red line) was used to evaluate membrane potential speed during the
 1573 transition. c) Average membrane potential speed in pyramidal neurons during optogenetically-
 1574 triggered and spontaneous down-to-up state transitions (paired Student's *t*-test, N = 11 cells from 4
 1575 animals, $p = 3E-4$). d-f) Same as in a-c but for optogenetic inhibition of SST interneurons (paired
 1576 Student's *t*-test, N = 9 cells from 5 animals, $p = 7E-1$).

1577 **Figure 5 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of the**
1578 **membrane potential speed during optogenetically-evoked and spontaneous down-to-up state**
1579 **transitions.**

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1582 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 1. Optogenetic activation of interneurons modulates network multi-unit**
 1583 **activity over large cortical territories in anesthetized animals.** **a)** Schematic representation of the
 1584 experimental setup. Simultaneous extracellular recordings are performed in anesthetized mice during
 1585 photoactivation of PV interneurons expressing ChR2. In this as well in other figures, Ch1 (red) indicates the
 1586 recording site located close to the illuminated area, whereas Ch2 (green) represents the recording site placed
 1587 2 mm away from Ch1 in the caudal direction. **b)** Top: example of a multi-unit signal recorded in Ch1 during
 1588 optogenetic activation of PV interneurons (blue line). Bottom: average PSTH of Ch1 for all recorded animals
 1589 (N = 10). **c)** Average frequency of spikes recorded in Ch1 before (Pre) and after (Post) light stimulation ($p =$
 1590 $3E-4$, paired Student's t -test, N = 10 animals). In this as well in other figures: grey dots and lines in this type
 1591 of graph indicate single experiments, red dots and lines indicate the average value represented as mean \pm
 1592 s.e.m. **d)** Top: multi-unit signal recorded in Ch2 simultaneously with the signal in Ch1 show in b (top panel).
 1593 Bottom: average PSTH of Ch2 for all recorded animals (N = 10). **e)** Same as in c but for recordings in Ch2 ($p =$
 1594 $3E-3$, paired Student's t -test, N = 10 animals). Green dots and lines indicate the average value represented
 1595 as mean \pm s.e.m. **f – j)** Same as in a – e but during photostimulation of SST interneurons expressing ChR2.
 1596 In h, $p = 9E-4$, paired Student's t -test, N = 9 animals. In j, $p = 4E-3$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, N = 9
 1597 animals.

1598 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of local PV**
1599 **activation on network activity over large cortical territories.**

1600 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 1 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of local SST**
1601 **activation on network activity over large cortical territories.**

Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2

1604 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 2. Large scale effect of PV and SST activation on multiunit activity**
1605 **using spatially-restricted DMD-based illumination. a)** Optical setup for patterned illumination with a
1606 DMD (see Methods for details). **b)** Schematic configuration for simultaneous extracellular recordings during
1607 photoactivation of PV interneurons expressing ChR2. The blue spot indicates the illuminated cortical region
1608 (200 μm diameter). **c)** Top: example of multi-unit signals recorded in Ch1 during optogenetic activation of
1609 PV interneurons (blue line). Bottom: average PSTH of Ch1 for all recorded animals (N = 7 animals). **d)**
1610 Average frequency of spikes recorded in Ch1 before (Pre) and after (Post) light stimulation ($p = 3\text{E-}2$,
1611 Wilcoxon signed-rank test, N = 6 animals). **e)** Top: multi-unit traces in Ch2 simultaneously recorded with
1612 signals in a (top panel). Bottom: average PSTH of Ch2 for all recorded animals (N = 6 animals). **f)** Average
1613 frequency of spikes recorded in Ch2 in the two time windows ($p = 3\text{E-}2$, N = 6 animals). **g-k)** Same as in b-f
1614 but during optogenetic activation of SST interneurons expressing ChR2. In i, $p = 2\text{E-}2$, Wilcoxon signed-
1615 rank test, N = 7 animals. In k, $p = 1\text{E-}3$, paired Student's *t*-test, N = 7 animals.

1616 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 2 – Source Data 1: Source data for the large scale effect of PV**
1617 **activation on multiunit activity using spatially-restricted DMD-based illumination.**

1618 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 2 – Source Data 2: Source data for large scale effect of SST**
1619 **activation on multiunit activity using spatially-restricted DMD-based illumination.**

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1623 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 3. Temporal lag of optogenetically-induced state transitions**1624 **across cortical areas. a)** Top: schematic of the experimental configuration for dual patch-clamp

1625 recordings from two cortical neurons (Ch1 and Ch2) located 2 mm apart during local optogenetic

1626 manipulation of PV cells in the area where Ch1 was recorded. Bottom: distribution of time lags

1627 (Ch2-Ch1 delay) of up-to-down transitions triggered by optogenetic activation of PV cells in the

1628 two simultaneously recorded neurons (bin width: 0.25 ms). **b)** Same as in (a) for optogenetic1629 activation of SST cells (bin width: 0.25 ms). **c-d)** Same as in a-b for optogenetic inhibition of PV

1630 (c) or SST (d) neurons (bin width: 10 ms).

Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 4

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1633 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 4. Local optogenetic modulation of interneurons modulates superficial**
 1634 **pyramidal neurons over large cortical territories in non-anesthetized animals. a)** Schematic
 1635 representation of the experimental configuration for intracellular recordings of superficial pyramidal neurons
 1636 in non-anesthetized animals during photoactivation of PV interneurons expressing ChR2. Recorded neurons
 1637 (Ch2, green) are located two millimetres apart from the illuminated region in the caudal direction. **b)**
 1638 Representative traces showing membrane potential effect of PV interneurons photoactivation (blue line)
 1639 during up states. **c)** Average membrane potential values before (Pre) and after (Post) light stimulation ($p =$
 1640 $7E-5$, paired Student's t -test, $N = 7$ cells from 3 animals). **d)** Schematic configuration for intracellular
 1641 recordings of layer II/III pyramidal neurons during optogenetic inhibition of PV interneurons expressing

1642 Arch in non-anesthetized animals. Light stimulation is delivered two millimetres apart in the rostral direction
1643 from the recording site (Ch2, green). **e)** Representative traces showing the effect of PV interneurons
1644 photoinhibition (yellow line) on the membrane potential of the recorded cell during down states. **f)** Average
1645 membrane potential values before (Pre), during (Light) and after (Post) light stimulation ($p = 1E-6$, one-way
1646 ANOVA, $N = 7$ cells from 4 animals). **g-l)** Same as in a-f but during optogenetic modulation of SST
1647 interneurons. In i, $p = 3E-4$, paired Student's *t*-test, $N = 6$ cells from 3 animals. In l, $p = 3E-4$, one-way
1648 ANOVA, $N = 9$ cells from 3 animals.

1649 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 4 – Source Data 1: Source data for the analysis of membrane**
1650 **potential changes in pyramidal neurons located 2 mm far from modulated PV and SST cells**
1651 **in awake mice.**

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1655 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 5. Local optogenetic inhibition of interneurons modulates network MUA**
 1656 **over large cortical territories in anesthetized animals.** a) Schematic of the experimental setup.
 1657 Simultaneous extracellular recordings are performed in anesthetized mice during photoinhibition of PV
 1658 interneurons expressing Arch.. b) Top: example of a multi-unit signal recorded in Ch1 during optogenetic
 1659 inhibition of PV interneurons (yellow line). Bottom: average PSTH of Ch1 for all recorded animals (N = 12)
 1660 c) Average frequency of spikes recorded in Ch1 before (Pre), during (Light) and after (Post) light stimulation
 1661 ($p = 1E-4$, Friedman test, N = 12 animals). d) Top: multi-unit signal recorded in Ch2 simultaneously with the
 1662 signal in Ch1 shown in b (top panel). Bottom: average PSTH of Ch2 for all recorded animals (N = 12). e)
 1663 Same as in c but for recordings in Ch2 ($p = 6E-4$, Friedman test, N = 12 animals). f-j) Same as in a-e but
 1664 during photoinhibition of SST interneurons expressing Arch. In h, $p = 2E-3$, Friedman test, N = 13 animals.
 1665 In j, $p = 2E-4$, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, N = 13 animals.

1666 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 5 – Source Data 1: Source data for the effect of local PV**
 1667 **inhibition on network activity over large cortical territories.**

1668 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 5 – Source Data 2: Source data for the effect of local SST**
1669 **inhibition on network activity over large cortical territories.**

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Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 6

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1672 **Figure 6 - Figure Supplement 6. Light transmission through the cortical tissue and density of opsin**
 1673 **positive cells. a)** Schematic representation of the illuminated brain volume using fiber optics. **b)**
 1674 Transmission fraction for yellow ($\lambda = 594$ nm) laser light as a function of the thickness of the cortical tissue.
 1675 The red curve indicates the fit that was used to calculate the scattering coefficient (see Materials and
 1676 Methods for details). **c)** Light intensity as a function of cortical depth. The intensity values are normalized to
 1677 the value at depth $z = 0$ mm. The inset shows the equation corresponding to the black curve. **d)** An
 1678 epifluorescence image of a representative coronal cortical section from a SST-Cre x TdTomato mouse
 1679 injected with Chr2-eYFP that was used to evaluate cell density. The blue line indicates the region where the
 1680 virus spread. The red line indicates the region with higher Chr2-eYFP expression, which was used for the
 1681 cell count of TdTomato positive cells (light cyan dots indicate individual TdTomato positive cells). **e-j)**
 1682 Representative confocal images of PV (top) and SST (bottom) interneurons expressing TdTomato and Chr2
 1683 used to evaluate the percentage of double labelled (TdTomato and Chr2-eYFP) cells. **k-l)** Total number of
 1684 TdTomato positive (TdTom) or TdTomato and Chr2 positive (TdTom + Chr2) cells in mice expressing
 1685 Chr2 in PV (shown in k) and SST (shown in l) interneurons. **m)** A box plot of the density of double-labelled
 1686 PV and SST cells in four different animals. The filled dots indicate the density values from all the individual
 1687 coronal sections that were analysed.

1688 **Figure 6 – Figure Supplement 6 – Source Data 1: Source data for the evaluation of light**
1689 **transmission through cortical tissue and of the density of opsin-positive cells.**

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